

TEKNISKA HÖGSKOLAN

HÖGSKOLAN I JÖNKÖPING

**Ontology-based Model For
The “Ward-round” Process in HealthCare
(OMWRP)**

Abid Ali Fareedi

MASTER THESIS 2010

INFORMATICS

TEKNISKA HÖGSKOLAN

HÖGSKOLAN I JÖNKÖPING

Ontology-based Model For The “Ward-round” Process in Healthcare (OMWRP)

Abid Ali Fareedi

This thesis is performed at Jönköping University, School of Engineering within the subject area Informatics, Specialization Information Engineering and Management. The thesis is part of the university’s master degree. The author is responsible for the given opinions, conclusions and results.

Supervisor: Vladimir Tarasov
Examinator: Kurt Sandkul

Credits point: 30 hp (D-level)

Date: 2010-06-08
Archive number:

Abstract

In the current arena, rapid changes are required to address dynamic patient's treatment process needs according to the patient's demand in the healthcare sector. This research work addresses existing problems about information flow in ward-round, what is the optimal information need for an individual with his/her competences according to their role during ward-round in healthcare area. This work also mentions what are the certain activities which are required during the patient treatment.

This research work contributes in the field of Information logistics and ontology development in healthcare. So the main purpose of this thesis is to design an ontology based model that can fix information flow problems in the ward-round process of hospital unit. The ontology based model can be used to provide relevant information to the domain users according to their needs and demands. The ontology based model projects domain users profiling and describes their roles, information demands with competencies: skills, qualifications and experiences. The ontology based model will be implemented in OWL language that can be used in an application to support ward-round activities for achieving effective patient's treatment process.

For ontology development is concerned, different ontology development methodologies have been reviewed from literature review by the author to analyze the existing problems in the ward-round. This thesis incorporates Hybrid Methodology (HM) that helps to develop ontology based model that addresses information flow problems in ward-round. The proposed ontology based model is developed in web Ontology Language (OWL) supported tool protégé 4.0.2 that can be considered as foundation to develop a software product with the help of IT practitioners and developers to fulfill medical practitioner's demands in ward-round's context.

Sammanfattning

I den nuvarande arenan, snabba förändringar som krävs för att hantera dynamiska patientens process måste enligt patientens efterfrågan i sjukvården. Denna forskning behandlar de problem om informationsflödet i församlingen runt, vad är den optimala informationen behovet av en individ med sin kompetens utifrån deras roll under avdelningen runt i sjukvården område. Detta arbete nämner också vad är vissa verksamheter som krävs under patientens behandling.

Detta examensarbete bidrar inom informationslogistik och ontologi utveckling i vården. Så det huvudsakliga syftet med uppsatsen är att utforma en ontologi baserad modell som kan lösa problem informationsflödet på avdelningen runt processer sjukhusenhet. Ontologin modell kan användas för att ge relevant information till domän användare beroende på deras behov och krav. Ontologin modell projekt domänanvändare profilering och beskriver deras roller, kräver information med kompetens: färdigheter, kvalifikationer och erfarenheter. Ontologin modell kommer att genomföras i OWL språk som kan användas i ett program för att stödja ward-runt aktiviteter för att uppnå effektiva patientbehandlingen process.

För ontologi utveckling berörs, olika ontologi utvecklingsmetoder har granskats av litteraturöversikt av författaren att analysera de befintliga problemen på avdelningen runt. Denna avhandling innehåller Hybrid Metod (HM) som hjälper till att utveckla ontologi baserad modell som tar upp problem informationsflödet i församlingen runt. Den föreslagna ontologi baserad modell är framtagna i webb Ontology Language (OWL) stödde verktyg skyddsling 4.0.2 som kan anses vara grund för att utveckla en programvara med hjälp av IT-utövare och utvecklare för att uppfylla läkare krav på vårdavdelning-rundan sammanhang.

Acknowledgements

First of all, I would like to modestly thanks to GOD Almighty, Who helps me and gives encourage to doing this research dissertation in good health. I want to present this thesis report to my beloved parents who are really keen in my success and pray in every minute of my life and helped me in stay here in Sweden.

I want to give cordially tribute to my supervisor (Vladimir Tarasov) who gives his wisely advices, support morally and socially and behaves as active knowledge mentor during my thesis work.

I would also like to say thanks knowledge mentors (Kläss Gäre and Eva Lindholm) who are responsible for conducting the modelling workshop to facilitate my thesis's acquiring knowledge and judgement.

I want to say thanks to all my friends who helped me while doing this research dissertation.

Key words

Ward-round, Ward-round Process, Information Logistic, Healthcare, Ontology Engineering, Ontology Development, Ontology Development Methodologies, Adaptive Workflow System, Healthcare Methodologies, Mixed Method, Hybrid Methodology, Action Research, Constructive Research, KPI, etc.

Contents

1	Introduction.....	1
1.1	BACKGROUND.....	1
1.2	PROBLEM.....	3
1.3	PURPOSE/OBJECTIVES	3
1.4	ASSUMPTION	4
1.5	DEMARCATON.....	4
1.6	THESIS OUTLINE.....	4
1.7	TIME PLAN	5
1.8	SYSTEMATIC WORKING PLAN	6
1.9	FINAL REMARKS	7
2	Theoretical Background	8
2.1.	DIMENSIONS OF INFORMATION LOGISTICS.....	8
2.2.	WARD ROUND	9
2.1.1	<i>Why Look At Ward Round?</i>	9
2.1.2	<i>Aspects of Ward-rounds</i>	10
2.3.	ONTOLOGY DEVELOPMENT	11
2.4.	ONTOLOGY DEVELOPMENT METHODOLOGIES	12
2.5.	ONTOLOGY DEVELOPMENT IN HEALTHCARE	12
2.5.1.	<i>Workflow and Data Exchange in Healthcare</i>	13
2.5.2.	<i>Adaptive Workflow System (AWS)</i>	13
2.5.3.	<i>Process and Resource Model (PRM)</i>	14
2.6.	APPROACHES USED TO MODEL ONTOLOGIES IN HEALTHCARE	14
2.7.	EXISTING ONTOLOGIES IN HEALTHCARE	16
2.8.	ONTOLOGY REUSABILITY	17
2.9.	FINAL REMARKS	17
3.	Research Methodological Approach	18
3.1.	TYPES OF RESEARCH METHODS.....	18
3.2.	HIGH LEVEL RESEARCH METHODS FOR INFORMATION COLLECTION	19
3.3.	LOW LEVEL RESEARCH METHOD FOR RESEARCH DESIGN.....	19
3.3.1.	CONSTITUTE OF MIXED METHOD RESEARCH DESIGN PROCESS (MM)	19
3.3.1.1.	<i>Action Research</i>	20
3.3.1.2.	<i>Action Research Implication Steps</i>	20
3.3.2.	<i>Constructive Research</i>	20
3.3.2.1.	<i>Constructive Research Implication Steps</i>	21
3.4.	Phases of Mixed-Method Research Design.....	21
3.5.	LOW LEVEL RESEARCH METHOD FOR ONTOLOGY DEVELOPMENT	26
3.5.1.	<i>Hybrid Methodology for Ontology Development (HM)</i>	26
3.5.2.	<i>Development Activities</i>	26
3.6.	METHODS FOR EVALUATION AND VALIDITY OF RESEARCH DESIGN.....	28
3.7.	DOCUMENTATION.....	28
3.8.	MANAGEMENT ACTIVITIES	28
3.9.	PHASES OF HYBRID METHODOLOGY FOR ONTOLOGY DEVELOPMENT.....	29
3.9.1.	<i>Motivating scenario</i>	29
3.9.2.	<i>Informal Competence Questions</i>	30
3.9.3.	<i>To build the Glossary of Terms</i>	30
3.9.4.	<i>To build the Concept of Taxonomy</i>	30
3.9.5.	<i>To define Ad-hoc Relations</i>	30
3.9.6.	<i>To define Ad-hoc Binary Relations in detail</i>	30

3.9.7.	To Define Constant in Detail.....	30
3.9.8.	To Define Formal Axioms Specification.....	30
3.9.9.	To Define the Classes and Class Hierarchy in Detail.....	31
3.9.10.	To Define the Properties of Classes and Class Hierarchy using Top-down Approach for Development.....	31
3.9.11.	To define Instance.....	31
3.10.	ONTOLOGY DEVELOPMENT WORK-FLOW MODEL.....	31
3.11.	FINAL REMARKS	32
4	Realization of Ward-round.....	33
4.1.	WARD-ROUND	33
4.2.	TRADITION WARD-ROUND.....	33
4.3.	MODERNITY WARD-ROUND	33
4.4.	OBJECTIVE OF WARD-ROUND	33
4.5.	CRITERIA FOR ADMISSION PROCEDURE (AP).....	34
4.5.1.	Steps are involved in Normal/Routine Admission Process	34
4.5.2.	Steps are involved in Emergency Admission Process.....	35
4.6.	COMPETENCE SELECTION CRITERIA.....	37
4.7.	CONCEPTUAL MODEL	39
4.8.	WARD-ROUND PROCESSES	41
4.9.	PRE WARD-ROUND PROCESS (PRWP).....	41
4.10.	WARD ROUND PROCESS (WRP)	53
4.11.	POST WARD-ROUND PROCESS (PWRP).....	71
4.12.	FINAL REMARKS	76
5.	Results.....	77
5.1.	MODELLING WORKSHOPS.....	77
5.1.1.	Modelling Workshop (I)	77
5.1.2.	Modelling Workshop (II)	77
5.1.3.	Ontology Reuse.....	78
5.2.	PROPOSED ONTOLOGY BASED MODEL FOR WARD-ROUND	78
5.3.	HIGH LEVEL ONTOLOGY BASED MODE FOR WARD-ROUND	78
5.4.	DETAIL ONTOLOGY BASED MODEL FOR WARD-ROUND	79
5.5.	MEDICAL STAFF.....	82
5.6.	ROLE.....	82
5.7.	ORGANIZATION.....	83
5.8.	RESOURCES.....	83
5.9.	COMPETENCE.....	85
5.10.	PROCESS	85
5.11.	GOALS.....	86
5.12.	ACTIVITIES.....	88
5.13.	MAIN SCENARIO MODELLING.....	88
5.14.	IMPLEMENTATION OF ONTOLOGY MODEL/RESULTS.....	92
5.14.1.	Domain Classes and Properties	95
5.14.2.	OWL Property Axioms.....	97
5.14.3.	Promising Role in Healthcare Business.....	98
5.14.4.	Implementation of Main Scenario Modelling.....	100
5.14.5.	Evaluation.....	102
5.14.6.	Final Remarks.....	103
6.	Conclusion and Future Work.....	104
7.	References	106
8.	Appendix	111
8.1.	TASK 1: MOTIVATING THE SCENARIO	111
8.2.	REQUIREMENT ENGINEERING.....	111
8.3.	NOTES FOR UNDERSTANDING FOR HEALTHCARE CASE STUDY	111

8.4.	SCOPE OF THE ONTOLOGY	112
8.5.	PURPOSE.....	112
8.6.	DOMAIN USERS	113
8.7.	TASK 2: COMPETENCE QUESTIONS POOL.....	113
8.8.	TASK 3: GLOSSARY OF TERMS	114
8.9.	CONCEPT TAXONOMIES	118
8.10.	DETAIL DIAGRAM FOR INDIVIDUAL'S ROLES	122

List of Figures

Figure Description	Page No.
FIGURE 1: TIME PLAN.....	5
FIGURE 2: SYSTEMATIC WORKING PLAN.....	6
FIGURE 3: WARD-ROUND.....	11
FIGURE 4: HEALTHCARE PROCESS REFERENCE HOUSE.....	14
FIGURE 5: CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF AN ONTOLOGY DRIVEN MULTI AGENT SYSTEM.....	15
FIGURE 6: LEVEL OF COMPETENCE MANAGEMENT AND THEIR INTERCONNECTION.....	15
FIGURE 7: EXISTING ONTOLOGIES.....	16
FIGURE 8: MIXED METHOD RESEARCH APPROACH.....	18
FIGURE 9: MIXED METHOD RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.....	23
FIGURE 10: ONTOLOGY DEVELOPMENT WORK-FLOW MODEL.....	29
FIGURE 11: HYBRID METHODOLOGY FOR ONTOLOGY DEVELOPMENT PROCESS.....	32
FIGURE 12: CONCEPTUAL MODEL FROM MODELLING WORKSHOP.....	36
FIGURE 13: THEORATICAL ADMISSION PROCESS.....	40
FIGURE 14: ACTIVITY ROLE MODEL: MEDICAL INVESTIGATION.....	44
FIGURE 15: PATIENT MEDICAL RESULTS FOR INVESTIGATION IN PATIENT'S TREATMENT PROCESS.....	45
FIGURE 16: ACTIVITY ROLE MODEL: UPDATE PATIENT LISTS FOR TREATMENT PROCESS.....	48
FIGURE 17: PATIENT MEDICAL RESULTS FOR INVESTIGATION IN PATIENT'S TREATMENT PROCESS.....	49
FIGURE 18: ACTIVITY ROLE MODEL: COLLECTION OF PATIENT MEDICAL PORTFOLIO.....	51
FIGURE 19: COLLECTION OF PATIENT MEDICAL PORTFOLIO PROCESS.....	52
FIGURE 20: ACTIVITY ROLE MODEL: PATIENT SHOULD DISCHARGE OR RETAIN.....	56
FIGURE 21: PATIENT SHOULD DISCHARGE OR RETAIN PROCESS.....	57
FIGURE 22: ACTIVITY ROLE MODEL: IMMEDIATE TREATMENT PLAN.....	63
FIGURE 23: ACTIVITY ROLE MODEL: LONG TERM TREATMENT PLAN.....	64
FIGURE 24: PATIENT TREATMENT PLANNING PROCESS.....	65
FIGURE 25: ACTIVITY ROLE MODEL: MEDICAL EDUCATION & LEARNING OPPORTUNITIES.....	69
FIGURE 26: MEDICAL EDUCATION & LEARNING OPPORTUNITIE PROCESS....	70
FIGURE 27: ACTIVITY ROLE MODEL: POST WARD ROUND GROUP DISCUSSION.....	74
FIGURE 28: POST WARD ROUND GROUP PROCESS.....	75

List of Abbreviations

AP	Admission Procedure
COSMIC	Electronic Medical Record
EBBA	Patient-admit System
AWS	Adaptive Workflow System
ILOG	Information logistics
PRM	Process and Resource Model
WRP	Ward Round Process
PWRP	Post Ward-round Process
HM	Mixed Method Research Design
IS	Information System
ILog	Information logistics
PRWP	Pre Ward-round Process
PH	Patient History

I Introduction

The introductory chapter depicts the selection of the research domain, importance of the research, the objective and limitation of the research work. It also includes the background of the problem domain and highlights what are the problem areas in the domain acquired from modeling workshop and literature investigation. The focus is on the purpose of research study and reflection to address research questions, discussion to achieve solutions.

I.1 Background

It has been proved through continuous business practices in the current arena [38], the influence of Information technology has proved and playing significant and productive contribution in every area of our social life and wide spectrum of business sector such as healthcare business etc. [3]. The optimized internal communication among different individuals and information flow in healthcare organization is very important [3][43]. To providing healthcare services to the users/patients is quite valuable in healthcare business so authentication of the relevant and timely information is required for patient's care demand in healthcare's organization.

In our discussion, it is important to optimize the relevant information which is received from different sources: personnel and information systems [40] because the information is the core of any organization. For tackling the information flow problems [41] and these aspects to take into account, an individual knows that he/she needs a certain kind of information for certain tasks according to his/her assigned roles to perform different activities to achieve certain goals. The other aspects are about the availability of the information in inter-organizational healthcare processes [42][41].

The main contribution of our work is related to information logistics (ILog) that aims at providing the right information to the right users at the right time and in right situation [41][3]. The information logistics concept emphasizes the advantages and possibilities of a demand-driven and person related information [43].

To understand the information logistics phenomenon, it is important to classify the roles of an individual who will participate in the context. According to their competencies levels and tasks assigning, information demands is described e.g. patient medical History [1] and information needs e.g. diseases information, ward-management information [1] to access certain contents sources e.g. health databases [1] at user's location e.g. at the hospital ward or at home [1].

From the previous study, it was noticed that the information flow is suffered due to the unavailability of the information at right time due to manual infrastructure and human's involvement in healthcare sector. So it is need to know what is the relevant information needs and demands for an individual according to individual's competence against assigned role. It is also important to mention which activities are useful to lead certain tasks in the ward-round session for effective patient treatment in healthcare sector. The healthcare sector will be improved with the incorporation of information technology based infrastructure. It contributes to manage content of

sources for timely information sharing according to the user demands [4]. For this purpose, I have to concentrate ontology based modelling that can be a solution for addressing information flow problems in hospital management and depicts information logistics concept that right information at right time for right individual in assigned situation in following chapters.

The relevant information helps to take decisions in healthcare business. This thesis is projected on the concept of Ward-round. Nowadays, rapid changes have been observed for the patient's requirements in healthcare sector, so we have to focus on reliable activities which are useful in patient's treatment procedure.

According to the modeling workshop and literature review, Ward-round usually happens in the hospital or medical institution to enhance the pace of healthcare for patient's treatment perspective. Ward round helps to motivate different perspectives of patient's care which is described in section 2.1.1. For conducting the ward-round, different activities happen on designated time regularly. In ward-round, some dedicated activities are when designated nurses are responsible for taking the patient primary information from COSMIC (Electronic Medical Record) for initial assessment during the patient admission process. According to nature of illness, designated nurses are responsible to send generic patient's medical test for getting the report status from laboratory. Some designated junior practitioners evaluate the patient's medical reports for initial treatment before going to ward-round treatment process. Junior practitioners have responsibilities to communicate with the designated nurse for collecting the patient's status from day and night observations while stay in particular ward or medical hospital/institution and also get the bed availability status from the head nurse who is responsible for managing the EBBA (Patient-admit System). Senior practitioners are responsible to inform consultant or specialized practitioners for ward-round treatment and also manage the resources used in ward-round. A senior practitioner also invites medical students to ward-round treatment process to educate the medical students for their grooming as professional.

Ward-round is a consortium of different caliber healthcare professional who have analytical assessment to incorporate different core activities in ward-round: patient examination and investigation, Refining the diagnosis, Treatment planning, Discharge planning, Interdisciplinary communication, and Learning opportunities [6]. Ward-round's primary perspective towards patient's health investigation, treatment process, discharge process from the medical unit [5] and secondary perspective is used to maximize educational opportunities for junior physicians, nurses and medical students. Ward-round is the decision making process that tempered by cost and availability of resources [5][6].

Every ward-round is specialized accordingly in the healthcare unit e.g. Cardiology department. So every assigned medical team is responsible for taking the decision in the patient's treatment in healthcare unit. For improving the intra communication among different ward-rounds in the healthcare organization [42], it is necessary that ward-round resources should be cooperated for communication purposes to maintain the quality patient's treatment process.

I.2 Problem

After analytical review and assessing the whole case study in the current study from the modeling workshop, it is realized that there are some issues in the current problem of ward-round in healthcare's organization. Due to information sharing and integration in the healthcare, we observe some information flow problems [41] which are lack of required relevant information for individuals according to their assigned roles in current situation of ward-round. We need to handle these information flow problems in healthcare to prevent harmful consequences [3].

- The existing problem in current case study is to identify information flow, what is the optimal information needs for an individual with his/her competencies according to his/her role while exclusive tasks? [1][2].
- The other issue is what are the activities utilized to make patient's treatment process effective in ward-round process.

I.3 Purpose/Objectives

This thesis work contributes to the field of Information logistics and ontology development in healthcare. The existing situation of the ward-round in the hospital is not very efficient to achieve quality patient's treatment process. So the main purpose of thesis is to design an ontology based model for information flow in ward-round processes. This model can be used to provide relevant information to the domain users according to their needs and demands.

The ontology based model is a solution to fix information flow problem in the ward-round in hospital unit. The one way to do it is to define hospital personal roles according to their competencies to perform certain activities in different tasks in ward-round processes in hospital unit. The ontology based model will be implementable in ontology language and can be used in an application to support ward-round activities for achieving effective patient's treatment process.

I.4 Assumption

- The individual role's information like (Consultant, Senior and Junior Practitioners, Head and Assistant Nurses, Occupational Therapists and laboratory personal) is already known from the modeling workshop session.
- The relevant competencies of roles (general, cultural and occupational) are already known from the modeling workshop session.
- The relevant resources like (EBBA, COSMIC etc.) which are utilized for performing the activities in ward-round process are already known from the modeling workshop session.
- The processes which are involved in the ward-round are already known in the modelling workshop session.

I.5 Demarcation

The demarcation is the act to limitize the scope of our study. The work presented to identify certain set of boundation and the functionalities are being used in this dissertation. These boundaries which we observe throughout case study analysis and discussion from the domain experts in the modeling workshop are listed below.

1. Our research dissertation is limitized to develop ontology-based model to give overview of the domain's discussion about ward-round.
2. This thesis will focus on patient's treatment activities with certain medical resource personnel in the given context (ward-round).
3. We are not targeting any particular healthcare unit in discussion, we are contributing to give the generic activities steps that will support in certain tasks while patient's treatment process in ward-round.

I.6 Thesis outline

The first chapter describes the background of my work, the purpose of the dissertation, problem identification, assumption which are used and demarcation in the domain's study. The second chapter describes about the theoretical background and related work. The third chapter describes research methodologies, mixed method research design to express in systematic way and Hybrid methodology which is used for ontology development process. The fourth chapter describes the realization: concept of ward-round, types of ward-round, functionalities and working of ward round and concerning results. The fifth chapter is about the results of ontology implementation which describes pictorial description of the modeling. The sixth chapter is about conclusion and future work related to our study and finally, we have discussed the conceptualization of the ontology in appendix [3].

I.8 Systematic Working Plan

Figure-2: Systematic Working Plan

The research work is initiated and based on modelling workshop with domain experts. This modelling workshop helps to write a case study to analyze current domain situation. This case study is modified with the help of literature review and verified to the domain experts for feedback. The output of this phase is to write Analytical Note for better understanding for user's convenience. The next phase focuses on listing of different Activities, distinct Roles, and different Tasks. This phase is also based on modelling workshop information and literature review knowledge. This next phase gives list of activities, tasks, goals and different roles. The output of this phase is to mention different steps which lead these activities in systematic way. The next phase is for selection of suitable methodology for ontology development. Different developed methodologies are used to achieve desired results. The next phase is about evaluation of the results through domain expert's assessment and using DL-Query.

1.9 Final Remarks

The first chapter depicts the importance of the research topic and highlights the objective of this research work. It also presents some limitations of the work which invites the researchers to target core problems of the domain's area healthcare. It also mentions the thesis outline which gives brief description of each chapter in this thesis. This chapter also focuses systematic working plan which is derived from modelling workshop with domain experts to understand and analyze the domain's problems and mentions different ways to evaluate modelling results.

2 Theoretical Background

This thesis work is the contribution in the knowledge of information logistics and ontology development in different domains [3]. The first phase supports the importance of information logistics, why we use information logistics and where we can utilize it in different applications related to healthcare domain's areas "*Personalized healthcare center portal*" [43] and used for the management of different tacit and explicit knowledge as information systems in the healthcare [44]. To address the concept of information logistics in healthcare we take "*The main objective of Information Logistics is optimized information provision and information flow. This is based on demands with respect to the content, the time of delivery, the location, the presentation and the quality of information. The scope can be a single person, a target group, a machine/facility or any kind of networked organization. The research field Information Logistics explores, develops and implements concepts, methods, technologies and solutions for the above mentioned purpose*"[41].

The information logistics role is also support information demand analysis and decision making in the context. The context based approach is used to support decision taken in the health care decision making process during the patient's treatment analysis [45]. To understand the concept of information demand context is "*An Information Demand Context is the formalized representation of information about the setting in which information demands exist and is comprised of the organizational role of the party having the demand, work activities related, and any resources and informal information exchange channels available, to that role*"[45]. The context (ward-round) means, the relevant information to a problem is available according to its need to handle the patient's treatment tasks or the information come from integrated sources to address quality patient's treatment process [45].

2.1. Dimensions of Information Logistics

Information logistics supports different dimensions content, time, location, representation, and quality related to healthcare contextual situation [41]. In this dissertation, our focus is on the improvement of the patient's treatment process. In patient treatment process context (Ward-round) we observe, what type of contents are needed for ward-round, at what time ward-round should call, where it happens and what is the representation of ward-round structure.

1. Content

The concept content represents the information to the participant; they are involved in the patient's treatment decision making process (ward-round) in this dissertation. The content is basically advice that you can deliver the content according to the situation in any domain's work [41].

2. Time

Healthcare business is very critical for patient's treatment point of view, so according to the current case study in this dissertation, timely information is the key relevant for conducting ward-round at certain time in healthcare management [41].

3. Location

Location is basically support where you want to use and who is the person who relatively wants to use the information, here in this dissertation, different medical resource personnel are needed to use relevant information in the patient's treatment process [41].

4. Representation

In this dissertation, the participants are used different reliable medium for the communication to improve the quality of the healthcare while ward-round. So, the representation of the same information into different form is helpful for understanding the context knowledge [41].

5. Quality

Quality attributes like reliability, authenticity of the data etc. are very important to lead quality patient's treatment process while ward-round.

2.2. Ward Round

The Ward-round has key roles, healthcare professionals are able to meet and develop an integrated plan of care in healthcare business [48][49][50]. The ward-round is a demonstration through hospital resource personnel are bounded to take some decisions concerning patient's treatment and care is concerned [5][6]. The ward-round facilitates, to provide an opportunity for the multi-disciplinary team to listen the patient's current illness situation and invites to make unanimous interpret his concerns [6][47].

2.1.1 Why Look At Ward Round?

Ward round is the situation, having different prime goals for the preparation of medical trainee at all levels and specific guidance to the trainees [6][46][47][51] and promotes unfolds diagnosis, management plans, prognosis and to trace out social, psychological rehabilitation issues during the patient's treatment process in ward-round [6].

We can see the overview of ward-round in the figure-3, Ward round also projects some key areas in the healthcare like improve the bed-side patient communication, Inter-professional communication while ward-round for good understanding or analysis and communication with the relatives to dig out more relevant information for better diagnosis or preparing good patient medical history and learning opportunities for the junior practitioner, medical students and nurses [6][49].

Ward-round promotes to enhance the patient management skills as well as multidisciplinary skills to perform different complex activities in the ward-round for quality patient treatments while the patient's stay in the hospital [46][30]. The main focus of ward-round is to achieve quality of care while patient treatment process, improving communication among

multidisciplinary team, promoting learning opportunity to educate the skills to the junior practitioners, nurses, occupational therapists and other concerning staff in treatment process [47][49][51].

2.1.2 Aspects of Ward-rounds

To emphasize on different aspects of the ward-round functionality in healthcare as follows [47]:

- **Planning for Patient Treatment**

The most important perspective of the ward-round is to educate the team members about their roles in patient treatment process and also invites to share the learning experiences and expertise to contribute in treatment procedures for quality healthcare [47].

- **Designated Timing for Patient Examination**

In ward-round, consultant or instructor normally spends designated time to discuss the progress of the patient's illness with the junior practitioners and other multidisciplinary team members as necessary [47].

- **Preparation for Patient Treatment**

It is important that, before going into the patient treatment process, the hospital resource personnel should maintain and up to-date patient's medical results for investigation [5], Update patient lists they need medical attentions [5] and Collection of patient's medical portfolio [5][47].

- **Patients**

Variety of patients are admitted in the medical ward to determine which diseases are discussed during ward-round [47]. After receiving the subject medical history, it is important to present demonstration of common disorders, represent problems that lend themselves to a discussion "*pathophysiology*" and patient's illness outside the participants area of expertise [47].

- **Location for Ward-round**

Location is very important factor to promote the trainees learning point of view. Most of the consultant or senior practitioners are advised to place the ward-round where patient is resided [47].

- **Discussion Format while Ward-round**

The discussion format for solving the problems should be flexible for understanding of all the participants in the ward-round so that participants can list down the problems in

detail, give them priority and initiate management steps to solve these problems. E.g a clinical skill format emphasizes acquiring complete and authentic patient medical history and physical examination reports [47].

- **Emphasis on Short-Term Manifestation**

For enhancing the learning opportunities in the ward-round process, consultant or senior practitioner should give mini-demonstration to address the problems in the ward-round process to the trainee, or medical students [47].

- **Trainee Participation in the Ward-Round**

Normally, it is observed that junior practitioner presents the case study for discussion. The main purpose is the involvement of junior practitioner in the current discussion and receive assessment from the senior. The main purpose is to assess the performance of the senior to appoint as role model for the junior members [47].

- **Assessment and Feedback**

Consultant and senior practitioners ensure that all members are required to present the patient's concern cases and respond to questions so that their performance can be evaluated during the ward-round process [47].

Figure-3: Ward-round [5]

2.3. Ontology Development

In this dissertation, we have focused on ward-round process and ontology development after receiving the extensive modeling workshop from domain experts and literature review about ontology development. To analyze the importance of the concept ontology: “*An ontology is an explicit specification of a conceptualization*” [52]. “An ontology defines the basic terms and

relations comprising the vocabulary of a topic area, as well as the rules for combining terms and relations to define extensions to the vocabulary” [53].

“Ontology as a specification of a conceptualization, Ontology as a philosophical discipline, Ontology as an informal conceptual system, Ontology as a formal semantic account, Ontology as a representation of a conceptual system via a logical theory Ontology as the vocabulary used by a logical theory. Ontology as a (meta-level) specification of a logical theory” [54]. *“An ontology is a hierarchically structured set of terms for describing a domain that can be used as a skeletal foundation for a knowledge base”* [55]. *“An ontology is a formal, explicit specification of a shared conceptualization”* [56].

Nowadays, It has been observing that the usage of ontologies are increasing not only in the artificial intelligence laboratories but also frequently using in different domains e.g. healthcare [3]. Due to some reason, ontology is used:

1. To provide common understanding of integrated information [3].
2. To reuse puposes of domain knowledge [3].
3. It is used to separate the domain knowledge from the operational knowledge [3].
4. It is also used for the analyis of domain knowledge [3].

2.4. Ontology Development Methodologies

There are many methodologies are used for the ontology development. For the construction of the domain model, number of methodologies that are precisely addressed the ontology development issues in different domains [19]. The construction of the ontologies is become an art and to make it an understood engineering process [19].

Methodologies describe the way to solve the problems in contextual situation (ward-round): *Tove* [19], [24], [26], *Methontology* [18], [19], [20], [22], [21], [23], [24], [25], *Enterprise Model Approach* [19], *KBSI IDEF5* (Knowledge Based Systems, Inc.) [19], *Model Driven Ontology* [57], *Ontolingua* [19], *CommonKADS and KACTUS* [19], *PLINIUS* [19], *ONIONS* [19], *Mikrokosmos* [19], *MENELAS* [19], *PHYSSYS* [19], *SENSUS* [19], *Guarino et al.* [19], *On-To-Knowledge Methodology (OTKM)* [58], *Rapid Ontology Development* [59], *ENHANCED METHODOLOGY* [23].

2.5. Ontology Development In Healthcare

The importance of the ontology in the healthcare has been acknowledged due to its usage nowadays in the healthcare industry. Ontologies are known for a formal declarative knowledge representation model [63]. The machine understandable knowledge can be obtained due to ontology utilization as a result to make machine intelligent. This technology has been using in healthcare sector for the patient’s treatment process and for achieving the quality healthcare services [63].

2.5.1. Workflow and Data Exchange in Healthcare

For quality healthcare services, there is need to have efficient healthcare workflow management systems which is useful for data exchange between different processes in the healthcare unit for healthcare professional [63]. For the easiness of the professional, the relevant data should be provided timely, effectively, and according to the demand of the individuals in the healthcare for the quality improved work [63]. Due to the awareness of information usage, workflow has become more popular gradually in different domains knowledge [3]. The domain's users are motivated by ontology-based workflow system to create, manage, and monitor workflows without influence of IT professional and it also highlights the shortcomings of existing system that is to assist process design at semantic level by utilizing context-aware, ontological knowledge and runtime process execution [3][63].

OWL (Ontology Web Language) is used in system that gives more expressive ontological description of complex relations between concepts [3][63]. Semantic Web services is used to deal with workflows and exchange data in healthcare enterprise to motivate the system which can coordinate the processes for the improvement of services of the system's tasks in real-time according to the context (ward-round) [3][63]. The motivation of workflows and data exchange is to boost up the quality of the healthcare services in healthcare industry [3].

2.5.2. Adaptive Workflow System (AWS)

In the research article [63], the system proposed name is Adaptive Workflow System (AWS). The functionality of the Adaptive Workflow System is to provide as base to describe patient context, healthcare processes, rules they lead to their processes activities and resources which are utilized to achieve these tasks in the healthcare [63]. The ontological framework [63] is helpful to understand the knowledge and information flow in the workflow system in following manner:

1. To arrange personnel workflow in the healthcare sector dynamically [63].
2. To excute the workflow automatically [63].
3. To monitor the performance of the system to evaluate the quality and effectiveness of the Adaptive Workflow System's services [63].

An Ontological knowledge framework [63] used in healthcare domains that covers the hospital encloses from patient records, hospital resources, and administrative tasks [3][63]. This system (AWS) facilitates and provides flexibility to care context-aware new medical workflows and execute them according to their requirement to all users in the hospital premises [3][63].

Figure-4: Healthcare Process Reference House [63]

2.5.3. Process and Resource Model (PRM)

As in figure-4, for good understanding of Adaptive Workflow System (AWS), it is important to construct process and resource model which shows different levels leads to complete the patient’s treatment processes [3][63]. It contains all the important relevant steps which involve in the different processes activities from patient’s admission, treatment planning, and patient discharge process. [3], [63]. For the development of the ontological knowledge framework, it is necessary to acquire corresponding domain context’s knowledge [3][63].

Siemens Medical Solution (MED) group and *Agency for Health Research and Quality (AHRQ)* are the two reliable sources for getting the domain knowledge in healthcare. [3][63]. Adaptive Workflow System (AWS), normally uses the *Siemens Health Process Reference [3]* for certain activities of processes related to certain tasks and assigned roles for the improvement of the quality, efficiency, safety, and effectiveness of healthcare [3][63]. In Key Performance Indicators (KPI) [63] in healthcare systems are supported to keep quality information related to patient’s treatment processes. The ontological knowledge framework is the comprised of role, organization, resources, KPI and processes involved [3][63].

2.6. Approaches Used to Model Ontologies in Healthcare

Different approaches are utilized to model Ontologies for healthcare nowadays. Archetype Patterns [60] is utilized for the ontology development in the healthcare information systems. Archetype supports the users in the healthcare domain to formally express their concept, secondly facilitate individual organizational healthcare information systems to fulfill the inter-enterprise standards: HL7 messages, LOINC, the national health data dictionary etc. and third enables the interoperability between healthcare processes [60]. Archetype patterns are considered the most promising approach to providing ontology for a shared understanding of healthcare processes [60].

Multi-agent approach is also utilized for healthcare [61], “Multi-agent systems provide a framework to help the patients, general practitioner, laboratory clinicians and specialists to interact and collaborate effectively” [61]. The interpretation of multi-agent system in the healthcare is described in the figure-5.

Figure-5: Conceptual Model of an Ontology-driven Multi-agent System [61]

Competence management is an approach used for goal-oriented shaping and healthcare’s individual competencies development in order to achieve enterprise competence [62]. To understand the competence management phenomenon, we analyzed the case study of Municipal Hospital of Karlsruhe [62]. The working of this approach is illustrated through following figure-6.

Figure-6: Levels of Competence Management and their Interconnections

2.7. Existing Ontologies in Healthcare

In the literature [65], ontologies have been used for a longer period of time to produce controlled lexicons for regulating schemes in medical informatics [65]. Bio-ontology has become quite mature field and lots of work has been done and new challenges have been left. The role of ontology in medical informatics is to share knowledge about a domain by modeling the things and show the relationships between them [65].

Nowadays, ontology based modeling has become significant in the bio-informatics and related to medicine and use of the ontology has been increasing tremendously in the healthcare industry. The usage of ontology based modeling helps to trace out the existing problems in the domain knowledge [3].

For the representation of the existing and new knowledge about the specific domain by using some ontology based models in which conceptualization is involved [3]. Classification is not similar to the ontology; it is the part of the ontology. An ontology, helps to describe, what we understand exists in our domain knowledge and what we try and capture, what are these to belong to one of the classes, categories or types in the model [3][65].

Figure -7: “Existing Ontologies” [65]

It is mentioned in the figure-7, in different period of time, there are different ontologies have been created according to the needs of Healthcare industry. EcoCyc [66] gives comprehensive encyclopedia of *Escherichia coli* biology. It is used for the integration of information about the genome, genes and gene products and it is regularly updated database [66]. TABIS (Transparent Access to Multiple Bioinformatics Information Sources) [67] is an application that is used by biologists to ask rich and complex questions over variety of bioinformatics resources. The key feature of TABIS and it is based on model which supports concepts and their relationships of domain knowledge in molecular biology and bioinformatics [67].

GALEN [68], for medical terminology, it is considered as large project developing terminology servers and data entry system based on common reference and core model [68]. The primary breakdown in the GALEN, is based on generalized-Structure [68], generalized-Substances [68], generalized-Processes [68] and Modifiers [68] and secondary structure aiming to capture the medical intuition of disease or disorder in the healthcare [68].

The other ontologies which are used in healthcare like Gene Ontology (GO) [69]; it is one of the successful and useful ontologies due to some feature of community involvement, goal clarification, early use [3]. Gene ontology (GO) is most promising tool for the representation and processing of information about gene products and its functions [69].

2.8. Ontology Reusability

Ontology reusability has been considered as important research issue in the ontology field in current arena [64]. According to literature [64], ontology reusability has two perspectives: first Integration and second Merging [64]. Integration perspective is composed of following sub-sections:

1. Integration

Integration is also represented into the form of

- Assembling
- Extending
- Specializaing
- Adapting other ontologies which are parts of the resulting ontology

2. Mergring

Merging different existing ontologies in your work as resulting ontology

In the literature [64], one of the promising features is the reusability of the ontology. The reusability of the ontology helps to save our precious time for the construction of the ontology from the scratch in our work. We can reuse the taxonomies, whole ontology or some part of the ontology in the domain knowledge [3].

2.9. Final Remarks

This chapter highlights significance of the research topic and mentions that what is the relation of this work with previous literature in certain domain of information logistic and ontology development. This chapter describes the main discussion about topic and what is the important and what is the need of this research in current arena.

This chapter also focuses the ontology development and ontology development methodologies for implementation is concerned in this thesis work. It also highlights the ontologies which are important in healthcare informatics. It also projects some approaches which are used to model ontologies in healthcare sector.

This chapter portraits about existing ontologies in healthcare which are useful for researcher to develop new customize ontologies especially in healthcare ontology modeling development. It also presents ontology reusability phenomenon and describes suitable techniques for ontology implementation in this research work.

3. Research Methodological Approach

In this part of the report, we emphasize the importance of the research methodological approaches: high level research method, low level research methods which are immensely useful for investigating the current problems and help to take initiative to find effective reliable solutions. These Methodologies invite the researchers to perform systematic, scientific and manageable quality work to address specific problem areas and mandatory domain's study.

The concept of research methodology is to support diligent, rigorous systematic process of investigation of the specific problem to describe effective solutions and develop test explanatory concepts, theories and applications [7]. According to the IEEE, the definition of the research methodology is described “A *comprehensive, integrated series of techniques or methods creating a general systems theory of how a class of thought-intensive works out to be performed*” [3][8]. This concept of research methodology is well explained in the following figure-8.

Figure 8- Mixed-Method Research Design

In this chapter, I have emphasized on high level research methods for information collection with the help of modelling workshop and discussion with knowledge mentors. I also describe low level methods for research design in my research work. I have chosen low level methods Mixed Method design process which is combination of Action research and Constructive research from the literature [9][11]. For development is concerned, I have chosen low level research method Hybrid Methodology for ontology development which is customized from Methontology [18] and TOVE [20]. I have also incorporate ontology development process in my research work with software development life cycle process in following section 3.10.

3.1. Types of Research Methods

There are mainly different research methods are used for investigation the specific problem to achieve effective solution in systematic way.

1. **High Level Research Methods for Information Collection**
2. **Low Level Research Methods for Research Design**
3. **Low Level Research Methods for Ontology Development**

3.2. High Level Research Methods for Information Collection

For information collection, I have used different methods in this research work. It has been discussed many high level methods for collecting the information. I have utilized following high level methods for information is concerned.

1. Modelling Workshop

The modelling workshop is taken as high level method which is the used for acquiring the relevant information from the domain experts during modeling session. I have taken modelling workshop in the start of my research work. The purpose of this modelling workshop is to understand the domain's problem and to specify the scope of the work. The domain experts were given the demonstration which was highly focused to investigate the problems and motivate the researchers for writing success case study for better understanding.

2. Discussion

Discussion is also considered as high level method for getting sensitive information from the domain experts. I have conducted meetings with domain experts and knowledge mentors for relevant, accurate and reliable information in my research work.

3.3. Low Level Research Method for Research Design

For the investigation of context problem's solution in this thesis related to healthcare unit, I have estimated and observed from case-study and contextual situation that there should be mixed method approach for investigation and analyzing the current situation of healthcare domain. I have considered and deployed two frameworks for research methodology in the current context of healthcare:

1. Mixed-Method Design Process

Mixed method design process is composed of action research and constructive research methods. The main purpose of mixed method research [9][10][11] is to provide framework where researchers can utilize for designing and conducting mixed method design process according to the contextual situation. Mixed method design process has become significant articulated, attached towards applied research practices in research paradigm along with action research and constructive research [11].

3.3.1. Constitute of Mixed Method Research Design Process (MM)

Mixed method research design process is targeting working mechanism in this dissertation to provide systematic guideline for good understanding to the readers.

3.3.1.1. Action Research

Action research is a collaborative approach to investigate systematically, the problems and their issues, to formulate according to the situations and develop the optimal plans to deal with the problems at certain situation or domain [12]. The main focus of action research is to identifying problems and helping for solutions in order to improve the current situation through investigation into human problems in real context of different discipline: Education [12], HealthCare [13]. Action research has been taken as mediator between medical staff and user, patient's participation in care process within healthcare unit. This study utilizes range of methods: interviews, questionnaires, documentary analysis and participation's observations for collecting the data for analysis [13]. It is observed that health science and action research are go together. Action research can be incorporated and utilized in different perspective of healthcare as health policy implementation, patient recruitment and patient treatment process and dissemination of the results [14].

The action research is taken as understandable, confidence finding process, controllable and truly practical approach by the context participants in healthcare because this approach is supported some flexible ways of finding the potential solutions to problems [14]. In current recent studies of health care, it is noticed that mostly medical staff is directly involved in action research and their aimed was to improve clinical, technological skills, and education to enhance the inter-communication among different staff members and service providers, to excel the management processes to lead the quality of patient's treatment mechanism and healthcare services are given to community in healthcare business [14].

3.3.1.2. Action Research Implication Steps

The steps are taken for carrying out action research differs from context to context but there are basic steps to follow [12]:

Step 1: The domain experts and researcher observe the situation with keen interest, working with those and define the place where the research is carrying out and describe the problems in detail to inquire along with a clear understanding of environmental knowledge or context of the problem situation [12].

Step 2: The domain experts and participants analyze and construct the situation to expand their understanding of the background and define the scope of the problem and identify the participants they are involved in the situation. At this stage, a general review of the literature can be carried out for situation's document authentication [12].

Step 3: The participant plan that will support to resolve the problems [12].

3.3.2. Constructive Research

The constructive research approach is taken as research procedure for producing novel constructs such as models, diagrams and plans to solve intended problems faced in the domain knowledge [15][16]. The Constructive research is considered one of the most popular methodologies in information system development and research field. The Constructive

research encapsulates different methodology development levels, the building processes, evaluation of construction results and action research [15]. Constructive research is to support problem solving ability in the selective and combine previous learned theories, procedures, declarative knowledge and cognitive strategies to solve the unknown problems in specific subject's knowledge [15].

According to [16], there are seven crucial steps are involved in the constructive research approach:

3.3.2.1. Constructive Research Implication Steps

The steps are taken for carrying out constructive research differs from context to context but there are basic steps to follow [16][3]:

- Step 1:** To find a practically relevant problems which have research potential?
- Step 2:** To examine the potential for long term research cooperation with the subjective organization.
- Step 3:** To create a generic and comprehensive understanding of the domain's problem.
- Step 4:** To innovate and develop a theoretical based solution to problem.
- Step 5:** To ensure that either it is implementable or not.
- Step 6:** To evaluate the scope of the solution's applicability and validity.
- Step 7:** To show the theoretical connections and research contribution of the solution.

The motivation to use the mixed method research design process in our thesis is to map the requirements of the thesis subject "Ward-round decision making process" in healthcare sector. In the start of the thesis, we collected the information from the experts in Ryhov, Jönköping, Sweden which is based on real-time problem in healthcare area about to develop intelligent decision making process for patient's treatment procedure. Here, the problem's requirement is projected the mixed-method research methodology because the participants are directly involved into the situation and they are looking for the optimal result which should be implementable according to healthcare need.

3.4. Phases of Mixed-Method Research Design

In mixed-method research design, there are different phases are involved in figure-7 to carry out this research methodology. These phases are listed down and I am very keen and optimist to achieve the desire results through this approach in my thesis.

1. Domain experts and researcher decide problem domain location or situation.
2. To prepare construct case study.
3. To define the scope of the problem's domain.
4. Describe and define the context problems detail with the change of environmental requirement.

- 5.** Define the goals and tasks.
- 6.** Compile relevant information from interviews, discussions, documentary analysis, observations and literature review.
- 7.** To design participation design plan.
- 8.** Development of constructs: Model, Plans, Design Solution.
- 9.** To Implementation or testing.
- 10.** Examine the scope of the applicability and validity.
- 11.** Show theoretical connection and research contribution from literature.

By utilizing the mixed-method research methodology in this thesis, the above steps as listed are followed to carry out the research process to meet the healthcare's goals perspective and optimal solutions in this research thesis's debate. This research process methodology is worked as iterative research with the change need because when the new requirements are required to get quality patient's treatment process.

Figure 9- : Mixed-Method Research Methodology

3.4.1. Description of Mixed-Method phases

The description of these steps is illustrated in following section.

3.4.2. Decide Problem's domain location or Situation

The domain experts and researcher are the responsible for assigning the domain where the problems are occurring. In this thesis, we have selected some problems in healthcare ward-round process. To fix these problems in particular situation, we have to propose ontology based modeling structure to educate the working activities to perform the certain tasks in the ward-round's problem.

3.4.3. To Prepare Construct Case Study

Enormous understanding of a certain problems in the given domain is the significant work of any proposed research work. For the quality work, it is very important to understand the domain contextual knowledge for analyzing the problem's nature and intimate effective solutions.

3.4.4. To define the Scope of the Problem's domain

For giving the optimal, efficient solution, it is necessary to mark boundaries of the domain's area of concentration. This strategy would help out for the usage of resources which are used in the domain's problems.

3.4.5. Describe and define the context problems detail

To describe the definition of the context problem's detail with the change of environmental requirement because in the initial stage of requirement gathering, we are not confident to cope up all the possible requirement form the domain's information sources.

3.4.6. Define the Goals and Tasks

In this part of the research, researchers define the main objective, goals and certain tasks in the analysis phase while understanding about the contextual knowledge of certain domain's problems. For achieving the objective of research in this thesis, we have to complete certain tasks: literature review, design the modeling construct, discussion with the experts, refine the model with feedback from the experts and domain users of healthcare and implementation of the ontology based modeling [3].

3.4.7. Compile relevant Information

For the initiative of any research or project, it is very important to have certain amount of information which facilitates the researcher for finding the relevant information from the information sources. The sources can be considered, interview from the domain experts, discussion forums, documentary analysis, observation and literature review. The major categories to acquire information are practical and theoretical [3]:

- **Practical**

For acquiring, practical information is concerned to use in our research work for solving the certain problems, we have conducted some structured or unstructured interview or arranged discussion with the domain experts who are involved in some empirical works [3].

- **Theoretical**

Theoretical data or literature review is considered the base of any research to continue the further research work in right direction. So we have discussed the certain domain problems with domain experts, they have been worked in the same research area for getting the good understanding from previous techniques, methods and approaches to solve the problems. If we have good literature review then we can go for authentic quality work [3].

3.4.8. To design participation design plan

At this stage, it is important to decide about the participant design plan according to their needs and demands of domain's problem.

3.4.9. Development of constructs: Model, Plans, Design Solution

After compiling the information from different relevant information channels, the most crucial part of the research is to use the knowledge to get initial result [3]. Here is the stage when we have developed the design model to illustrate the problem domain by using different methodologies or techniques. The personal skills and competences are involved to build the domain model at this stage [3].

3.4.10. To implement Design or Testing

For developing prototype, it is necessary to implement the design for testing perspective to ensure that prototype is fulfilling the domain's user's requirements.

3.4.11. Examine the scope of the Applicability and Validity

At this stage of implementation, then we have demonstrated to domain's experts to verify the scope of the modeling prototype and for getting comments and feedback to evaluate the validity regarding our work [3].

3.4.12. Show theoretical connection and research contribution from literature

At this stage, after refining the model which we have defined, what we have done in the specific domain's problem, what are our contributions in this research area, what are the significant perspective for domain's users and the model which we developed could be part of healthcare system in Sweden to regulate the information flow between different roles involved in this system [3].

3.5. Low Level Research Method for Ontology Development

For ontology development, I have chosen hybrid methodology for ontology development. Hybrid methodology is discussed in the following section.

3.5.1. Hybrid Methodology for Ontology Development (HM)

For the ontology development process, hybrid methodology is highly customized from the [18], [20] and [24]. It is used for the development of the ontology in healthcare area. After completing designing phase, we have to concentrate on the ontology development process. This model will serve as base to test ontology and validate its result [3]. This customized methodology will be representation of true scientific work in this research thesis.

Before going into the detail of ontology development phases, we have to take some primarily steps that are very critical and important to test our model according to the ontology development. These following steps as following:

- Step 1:** I have taken the relevant information from the domain (Healthcare) experts from the modeling workshop in Rhyov.
- Step 2:** I have developed case study or understanding notes for carrying out the research according to the situation (ward-round) in healthcare.
- Step 3:** I have proposed methodology for ontology based modeling to address domain's situation (ward-round) in healthcare from literature review which is called Hybrid methodology. Hybrid methodology is merger of Methontology and Tove (Toronto Virtual Enterprise) and described in detail 3.4.2 section.
- Step 4:** I have suggested protégé 4.0.2 tool which is used for ontology based model development.

Hybrid methodology is used for ontology development process. It takes some inspirations from the software engineering paradigm to develop it, well applicable and follows all phases which are involved in process orientation in software development life cycle (SDLC) [3]. Here we have used some activities these are very important part for the ontology development in the health care domain. This approach is constituted of different activities in following sections.

3.5.2. Development Activities

In this section, I emphasize on what are the important steps are involved to take different phases of development activities.

3.5.2.1. Pre-Development

1. Requirement Specification

These are the certain steps are involved while requirement specification phase.

1. Motivating scenario..... (Tove: Toronto Virtual Enterprise) [19].
2. Informal competency questions.....(Tove: Toronto Virtual Enterprise) [19].
3. To build the glossary of terms.....(Methontology) [18].

3.5.2.2. Development

These are the certain steps are involved while conceptualization process phase.

1. To build concept taxonomies (Methontology) [18].
2. To define ad-hoc relations.....(Methontology) [18].
3. To define ad-hoc binary relations in detail.....(Methontology) [18].
4. To define constant in detail(Methontology) [18].
5. To define formal axioms specification (Tove: Toronto Virtual Enterprise) [19].

3.5.2.3. Implementation

6. To define the classes and class hierarchy in detail.
7. To define the properties of classes and class hierarchy using top-down approach for development [17].
8. To define instance (Methontology) [18].

3.5.2.4. Supportive Activities

In hybrid methodology for ontology development process, there are involved different supporting activities, some of them are utilizing in this thesis but rests of the activities are out of the scope of our thesis work.

1. Knowledge Acquisition

Knowledge acquisition is the process to extract the information from domain experts and resource personnel; they are involved in the project for establishing good understand about the case study from modeling workshop in this thesis.

2. Ontology reuse

Reusability phenomenon is one of the best feature in the ontology development [3]. We can utilize and modify existing ontologies in that ontology which is being used. There are different reuse processes to reuse existing ontologies like integration and merging the ontologies [64]. Merging technique is used to reuse different ontologies in same subject's knowledge into that ontology which is being considered for reuse of same subject's knowledge [64]. Integration technique is used of building an ontology in one subject by reusing different ontologies of different subjects [64].

a. Merging

For reusability of the ontology is carried out in this research work through merging technique. I have chosen merging technique for building ontology in one subject reusing two or more different ontologies that is being used [64].

3.6. Methods for Evaluation and Validity of Research Design

The evaluation activity is involved in throughout ontology development process in this research work. At this stage, the evaluation and validity of the research design is the vital activity to ensure quality that all the requirements are met in ontology development process. So it is important to check the validity and inconsistency in the ontology development process. The developed ontology will be evaluated and validated through some practices:

1. The evaluation activity can be confirmed through DL-Query that gives the answer of competency questions from the ontology development model.
2. The evaluation activity is verified and evaluated through domain's experts assessment especially in my research work. Healthcare domain's experts are responsible to give feedback for improvements.
3. The evaluation activity is also assessed through domain's users who are being involved in the research study at the time of software prototype deployment.

3.7. Documentation

Documentation is the final product in the form of report in the thesis work.

3.8. Management Activities

1. Scheduling

Scheduling is concerned about the activities which are carried out by the ontology developer and domain's resources like information systems, hospital personnel, competencies, etc are used to achieve these certain activities at different levels of development in this thesis.

2. Control

Controlling is the mechanism to assure that all the activities are governed according to set plan by the researcher in the ontology development process.

The hybrid methodology for ontology development process is well expressed in the following figure-10 for understanding in pictorial form.

Figure 10-: Hybrid Methodology for Ontology Development Process

3.9. Phases of Hybrid Methodology for Ontology Development

3.9.1. Motivating scenario

Motivating scenario is taken from Tove methodology for writing the context of the problem. It is important to understand the need of this research work in healthcare. Why researchers are looking for the solution in ward-round process to take some vibrant decision for quality patient’s treatment?. I have explained about the case study in this research work in appendix section 8.3.

3.9.2. Informal Competence Questions

A Competence question concept is taken from Tove methodology. It is necessary for the domain users to get optimal results from the ontology based model and that model qualifies competence questions which I have presented in the appendix section 8.7.

3.9.3. To build the Glossary of Terms

The glossary of terms steps comes from Methontology method which describes about the concepts which are used in the ontology development and relations between them. The glossary of terms also defines the concepts description in briefly. I have presented the table-6 in appendix section 8.8 for user's convenience.

3.9.4. To build the Concept of Taxonomy

The concept taxonomy is very important for classification of concepts in the development phase and this concept comes from Methontology method. I have presented some taxonomy in appendix section 8.9 for reader's understanding.

3.9.5. To define Ad-hoc Relations

It comes from Methontology method and it defines the relationship between the concepts. The ad-hoc relations can be created from the domain knowledge or context of the problem.

3.9.6. To define Ad-hoc Binary Relations in detail

This step describes the ad-hoc binary relations in detail which comes from the Methontology method. This steps covers domain and range of the relations, what is the subject and what is object?. It also describes the association levels in terms of cardinality between concepts in binary relations. This step also projects the inverse relationship in binary relations.

3.9.7. To Define Constant in Detail

This step is taken from the Methontology in development phase. This step supports the constant value in terms of integer, strings etc. in data properties for the development of modeling prototype. For example hasAge is the data property and it is used to define the age of the individuals they are participating in the ward-round processes.

3.9.8. To Define Formal Axioms Specification

This step is taken from the TOVE methodology. This step defines the specification of axioms which is also known as closure axioms. The closure axioms implement on property (Object Property) with universal restriction. E.g. the closure axiom is applied on the (utilizeResource some Resource) similarly (isAssignRole min 1 Person). These expressions show the object properties like utilizeResource and isAssignRole for classes Resource and Person in the development prototype.

3.9.9. To Define the Classes and Class Hierarchy in Detail

In implementation phase, we try to maintain the class hierarchy in detail for user understanding. E.g. the person class has subclasses of different individuals like MedicalMember and MedicalStudent in the modeling prototype.

3.9.10. To Define the Properties of Classes and Class Hierarchy using Top-down Approach for Development

For the development of ontology based modeling, I used the top-down approach for implementation so that the classes can be presented in detail.

3.9.11.To define Instance

This step comes from the Methontology methodology. It represents the instances of classes that help to describe the actual working of the classes in the given situation. E.g. Ander Bill is the instance of MaleMedicalPractitioner that has Role (JuniorPractitioner).

3.10.Ontology Development Work-Flow Model

The Hybrid methodology steps are used to map with software development life cycle process steps which is illustrated in figure-10. The main objective of this work-flow model is to give software development pattern in ontology based modelling. I have considered software development life cycle phases in my ontology development to ensure that development is going on in systematic way and following the software development phases like (Requirement analysis, Design analysis & Refinement, Implementation, Evaluation, Maintenance etc).

Figure 11-: Ontology Development Work-Flow Model

3.11. Final Remarks

This chapter mentions about research methodological approaches which are immensely useful for investigation the current problems in healthcare area. This chapter focuses on different types of research methods; High level research methods for information collection like Modelling Workshop, Discussion and Low level research methods for research design like Mixed method design process and Low level research methods for ontology development like Hybrid methodology for ontology development.

This chapter also discusses different steps in detail in figure-9 and figure-10 which are taken to perform Mixed method design process and Hybrid methodology (HM) for ontology development. It also mentions different methods in section 3.6 for evaluation and validity of research design in thesis work.

4 Realization of Ward-round

This chapter presents the realization of Ward-round which I described in the beginning of report.

4.1. Ward-round

Ward-round is the platform where hospital's professional and resource personnel take decision making concerning patient's treatment process [6]. Word-round gives opportunity to the multidisciplinary team to carry out different activities patient's investigation, patient treatment and discharge from hospital [5], patient treatment plan, prognosis formulation and opportunity to analyze social, psychological, rehabilitation and placement issues [6] and supporting learning opportunities [27]. To improve the quality of patient's care, there are some vibrant changes are needed to enhance the effectiveness of the patient's treatment process by using some ways of healthcare like: use of electronic notes [28] and information system for timely information gathering in ward round for performing patient's related activities.

4.2. Tradition Ward-round

Traditional ward-round is led by some senior hospital personnel: consultant and senior doctors with junior doctors, medical students, nursing staff, occupational therapists and other healthcare professional to analyze the current situation, and enable to make decisions [6]. In traditional ward-round, the consultant was being autocratic having responsibility to take decision in patient's treatment process.

4.3. Modernity Ward-round

Due to medical education awareness, the arena is totally changed. The consultant and senior expertise are negotiated and made consensus and inclusive listening of house staff, nurse, specialist's nutritionists, pharmacists, occupational therapists and occasionally administration to improve the quality of healthcare for patient's service perspective [6].

4.4. Objective of Ward-round

The objective is to achieve certain benefits by applying modernity ward round approach in current practices of healthcare industry. These objectives are marked as validating history and physical examination, refining diagnosis, prognosis, treatment planning, admission procedure, discharge planning, interdisciplinary communication, cost analysis, patient's treatment priority setting, patient communication with hospital personnel communication with relatives [6] and teaching and learning opportunities[6][27].

Ward-round also emphasizing to forming a new ways of working which could be understood from three concepts. These concepts are, "*bound by tradition*", "*Juggling the change*", "*light at the end of the tunnel*" [30]. The first concept is emphasized how the traditional ward round represent a double sword [30]. One perspective is to provide safe structure and also highlight the share awareness of an urgent need to leave of old ways of working behind. The safe

structure emphasizes degree of stability and control, having the awareness about the number of challenges concern with ward-round [30]. The concept, “*light at the end of the tunnel*” is the process of reformation of the traditional ward-round which could be considered as valued and realistic, flexibility factor is the main strength of this concept. It is essential and important to take systematic and contextual information in the successful incorporation of any change initiative [30].

Before considering the ward-round processes for patient treatment, it is important to evaluate the nature of the patient at the time of admission. The criterion for admission is found in the section 4.5.

4.5. Criteria for Admission Procedure (AP)

For assessment and evaluation of the patient’s illness, it is important to define the certain criteria [33] to admit the patient in the hospital. The patients for admission or referred by some other institution are entertained according to the interaction perspective. These interactive perspectives are discussed according to “*diagnosis*” [33], “*symptomatology*” [33], “*better or worse prognosis*” [33], “*level of social support/patient autonomy*” [33], “*structure of the health network itself*” [33]. To understand the work flow of the admission process, it is necessary to accommodate the necessary steps before going the ward-ward processes.

For the improvement of the quality of the admission process in healthcare, we need to define the admission process which supports the admission procedure criteria. The steps are involved in the admission process as follows [34]:

4.5.1. Steps are involved in Normal/Routine Admission Process

The steps are taken from [34] for understanding and judge the working flow of patient’s admission process in normal/routine admission process and emergency admission process. These steps are illustrated for understanding as following in the figure-13 [34]:

Step 1: Registration in admission department

For patient’s admission process, it is important to bring the patient for admission department either in normal capacity or in emergency. The admission process is based on certain criteria [33].

Step 2: Examine the criteria of patient’s diseases symptoms

It is essential to ask about the patient’s admission criteria according to certain symptoms and diseases [33].

Step 3: Providing admission Performa and required information

For patient’s admission process, it is important to provide admission requirements, Performa, information and relevant documentations.

Step 4: Completion of patient's admission

After completing the formal requirements of any healthcare organizations for patient admission is concerned then sends the patient into the medical ward for examining in the ward-round processes.

4.5.2. Steps are involved in Emergency Admission Process

The certain steps are involved to describe the emergency admission process [34]. The step 1 is the primarily step to lead the second step.

Step 2: To provide prioritize medical attentions to attend the patient

In this step, it is very important that the hospital medical staff: physicians, nurses, technicians, etc are giving fully medical attentions to attend the patient in severe conditions.

Step 3: Waiting for the initial medical test for initial examination

In this step, hospital staff waiting for the initial medical test of patient to analyze or examine the nature of disease or injuries for admission's purposes.

Step 4: Providing admission Performa and required information to the patient's relatives

In this step, it is clarify to acquire maximum information related to the injury from the relatives and give information for the formal documentation.

Step 5: Negotiate with the relatives of the patient

After the examination procedure, it is necessary for operation perspective; make negotiation with relatives for operation to cure patient's illness or injuries.

Figure-12 Theoretical Admission Process [34]

After completing the admission procedure for patient, it is important to know whom medical members are assigned to conduct ward-round processes and what are the competences level they have to perform certain roles and responsibilities. As in table-1, a competence selection criterion is described different parameters to select right person for the right place for taking some initiatives in the patient's treatment process.

4.6. Competence Selection Criteria

Competence Selection Criteria is the minimum limitation for the hospital personnel to follow some certain rules of organization so that quality of the work can be achieved in the patient's treatment process. To understand the working of competence selection criteria, we take an overview of involved personal that is responsible to initiate some processes related to patient's treatment and certain processes are initiated by competence of the hospital personal during patient's treatment process.

Competence Selection Criteria function is the responsible to filter the information according to the proficiency level of hospital personnel or users [3]. The selection criterion is referred from [74].

Competence Selection Criteria	
Consultant	Senior Practitioner
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Education Competence = MBBS, MBChB, BMed, Dr. med [70]. 2. Work Experience Competence = 8-10 years 3. Skill Level = 7th level as described in International classification of Skill Level (ISCO) [21] [3]. 4. Language Skill level = Excellent 5. Language Competence: Swedish, International Language (English) etc. 6. General Competence = Excellent 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Education Competence = MD, MDCM, Cand.med, DO [70]. 2. Work Experience Competence = 5-6 years 3. Skill Level = 6th level as described in International classification of Skill Level (ISCO) [21] [3]. 4. Language Skill level = Excellent 5. Language Competence: Swedish, International Language (English) etc. 6. General Competence = Excellent.

<p style="text-align: center;">Junior Practitioner</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Education Competence = MD, MDCM, Cand.med [70]. 2. Work Experience Competence = 2-3 years 3. Skill Level = 5th level as described in International classification of Skill Level (ISCO) [21] [3]. 4. Language Skill level = Excellent. 5. Language Competence: Swedish, International Language (English) etc. 6. General Competence = Excellent 	<p style="text-align: center;">Head Nurse</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Education Competence = BSN, BNurs, BScN, BSc, MN [70]. 2. Work Experience Competence = 5-6 years 3. Skill Level = 5th level as described in International classification of Skill Level (ISCO) [21] [3]. 4. Language Skill level = Excellent. 5. Language Competence: Swedish, International Language (English) etc. 6. General Competence = Excellent 7. Specialized Field = experience depending on specialty like surgery, general etc.
<p style="text-align: center;">additional Nurse</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Education Competence = BSN, BNurs, BScN, BSc, MN [70]. 2. Work Experience Competence = 2-3 years 3. Skill Level = 4th level as described in International classification of Skill Level (ISCO) [21] [3]. 4. Language Skill level = Good. 5. Language Competence: Swedish, International Language (English) etc. 6. General Competence = Excellent 7. Specialized Field = experience depending on specialty like surgery, general etc. 	<p style="text-align: center;">Occupational Therapists</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Education Competence = MOST, MAOT, MOT, OTD, Dr.OT [70]. 2. Work Experience Competence = 5-6 years 3. Skill Level = 4th level as described in International classification of Skill Level (ISCO) [21] [3]. 4. Language Skill level = Excellent. 5. Language Competence: Swedish, International Language (English) etc. 6. General Competence = Excellent 7. Specialized Field = experience depending on specialty like surgery, general etc.

Medical Student	Administrator
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Education Competence = MSPAS [70]. 2. Work Experience Competence = beginner. 3. Skill Level = 4th level as described in International classification of Skill Level (ISCO) [21] [3]. 4. Language Skill level = Good. 5. Language Competence: Swedish, International Language (English) etc. 6. General Competence = Excellent 7. Specialized Field = beginner 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Education Competence = MHA, MPH [70]. 2. Work Experience Competence = 7-10 years. 3. Skill Level = 6th level as described in International classification of Skill Level (ISCO) [21] [3]. 4. Language Skill level = Excellent. 5. Language Competence: Swedish, International Language (English) etc. 6. General Competence = Excellent

Table-1 Information Selection Criteria

4.7. Conceptual Model

Conceptual model is the pictorial interpretation of the working flow from modeling workshop in the figure-12. Here, we observe ward-round as context in healthcare institution: Ryhov. For ontology based modeling development, it is necessary to reuse some existing ontologies about competence and diseases ontologies in current research study.

Ward-round is the centre of activities where different hospital professionals gather for the patient's treatment analysis. Here, in ward-round, different tasks are nominated according to the patient's illness for patient's treatment concern. Different individuals have different roles and ward-round has different goals for achieving quality healthcare services in patient's treatment process. These goals have different activities to fulfill these goals in patient's treatment processes because each goal has different tasks so for the completion of each task different resources are involved.

Resources can be considered as patient's treatment documents, medical equipment, information systems, competence models according to the individual's skills and qualification, and database systems.

Figure-13 Conceptual Model from Modelling Workshop

4.8. Ward-round Processes

Ward-round process is taken into account for three sub-processes they support consequently each other. Before going into the ward-round process, we have to analyze the initial works for patient treatment process. These sub processes are named as pre-ward round process (PRWP), ward-round process (WRP) and post ward-round process (PWRP) [5].

- 1. Pre Ward-round process (PRWP)**
- 2. Ward-round Process (WRP)**
- 3. Post Ward-round Process (PWRP)**

4.9. Pre Ward-round Process (PRWP)

For pre ward-round process (PRWP), it is important to designate a hospital personnel team: junior practitioner, additional nurses, occupational therapists, laboratory hospital person who they are responsible to manage different tasks: Make assurance that results are up to-date, Update patient lists, Collection of patient medical notes in pre ward-round process. These tasks can be achieved through some activities as input for ward-round process.

Designated team 1:

Different medical personnel are divided into different teams. These groups of personnel are used to take pre ward-round process (PRWP) activities as follows:

- Junior practitioner
- Head Nurse
- Additional Nurses
- Occupational therapist
- Laboratory Hospital Personal
- Medical Administrators

The description of the designated team1 can be seen in the figure-14 and figure-15 respectively.

1. Tasks

- 1.** To get satisfaction of the patient medical results for investigation are upto date in patient's treatment process [5].

2. Activities

There are the certain activities which helpful for achieving the above task [5].

- 1.** To assign relevant hospital personnel for initial examination of patient's treatment.

2. To evaluate and judge the competence levels of hospital staff in particular ward according to the nature of patient's illness.
3. To prepare critical medical history of certain diseases for patient.
4. To get current status of initial patient's medical test like blood test, urine test etc.
5. Head nurse gets the status report for availability of the bed's utilization from EBBA, to ensure that patient can be admitted or move some where else.

3. Roles

1. Medical administrator assigns the nurses and junior practitioner to prepare critical medical history of certain diseases for patient.
2. Medical administrator appoint domain's specialist additional nurse and junior practitioner for initial examination of patient's treatment.
3. Medical administrator has authority to judge and evaluate the hospital personnel according to their past working experiences and educational competences.
4. Additional nurse send the initial tests to the laboratory personnel for examination.
5. Head nurse is responsible for getting the status from the EBBA patient-admission status system.
6. Head nurse is managing the particular ward for timely ward-round process.
7. Laboratory personnel will send the medical tests report to the additional nurse and junior practitioner.
8. Occupational therapist is used to acquire legacy information from the patient and his/her relatives for optimizing patient's treatment process.

4. Goals

1. To achieve quality patient's treatment management plan in ward-round process [5].
 - a. The patient's medical results in patient treatment process should be verified by relevant resource personnel.
 - b. The patient's medical results should be received timely due to smooth working flow among different information channels for patient's treatment process.

5. Competence

1. Medical administrator needs work_Experience competence [32] (more than 8-10 years depending on speciality) and Educational competence [32] (Medical health Administration (MHA, MPH) [70]) to assign the most relevant hospital personnel for preparing medical history of the patient.
2. Nurses need language competence (Native language: Swedish, English etc) [32] to communicate with patient for investigation.

3. Junior practitioners need language competence (Native language: Swedish, English etc) [32] to communicate with patient for investigation.
4. Occupational therapists need cultural competence (Intercultural sensitivity, Native language, Swedish, English etc) [32] for acquiring relevant information from the patient's and his/her relatives.

6. Resources

For initially pre ward-round process (PRWP), the resources are utilized according to the domain's health care analysis are:

1. Medical staffs: Junior practitioner and nurses are used as resource to carry out patient treatment process.
2. Occupational therapist is used as resource for acquiring the information from the patient and his/her relatives.
3. Laboratory hospital personnel is used to laboratory database as resource to maintain the status of patient's medical tests.
4. Junior practitioners and nurses are used to take patient's record information from COSMIC (Electronic Medical Record System).
5. Hospital resources: particular ward, medical equipments are taken for investigation.

Realization of Ward-round

Figure –15 Patient medical results for investigation in patient’s treatment process

1. Tasks

The description of the designated team1 can be seen in the figure-16 and figure-17 respectively.

2. Update patient lists who are under consideration for medical treatment [5].

2. Activities

There are the certain activities which helpful for achieving the above task [5].

1. Write down in detail patient's concerning personal information from patient or COSMIC.
2. Presenting complaints while patient stay in hospital or treatment process.
3. To assess the seriousness of the patient's current illness with mutual consensus of junior practioners and nurses.

3. Roles

1. Additional nurses are responsible for writing down in detail patient's concerning personal information from patient or COSMIC.
2. Additional nurses inform to the junior practioner for complaints while patinet's stay in hospital or treatment process on daily basis.
3. Junior practioners are responsible for presenting the complaints of patient's current investigation to the seniors or consultant in ward-round process.
4. Junior practioners responsibility is to call pre-meeting before going reports into ward-round process.

4. Goals

1. To notify the senior about patient's overall condition is improving or deteriorating [5].
 - a. To create interaction with the patient to avoid distressing while initial investigation.

5. Competence

1. Nurses need cultural competence [32] (Language Level: Swedish, English,etc.) and Educational competence [32] (Bachelor in Nursing: (BSN, BNurs, BScN, BSc, MN)) to write down patient's concerning personal information.
2. Junior practitioners need occupational competence [32] (Language: Swedish, English) and Educational competence [32] (MD; MDCM, Cand.med, DO), work_Experience competence [32](2-3 years) to evaluate the nature of the complaints which will be presented in the ward-round process.

6. Resources

For the achievement of the task, there are certain resources are utilized for performing above activities.

1. Medical staff: additional nurses and junior practioners are involved to update patient list who are under consideration for treatment.
2. Hospital resources: particular medicalward, writing notes.

Figure -16 Activity-Role Model: Update Patient Lists for Treatment

Figure –17 Update patient lists for medical treatment Process

1. Tasks

The description of the designated team1 can be seen in the figure-18 and figure-19 respectively.

3. Collection of Patient Medical portfolio [5].

2. Activities

There are the certain activities which helpful for achieving the above task [5].

1. To gather important findings related to patient during examination or observations.
2. To collect the patient's related documents or notes for optimizing patient's treatment process.
3. To gather the information about certain diseases from patient's relatives for better patient's examination process.

3. Roles

1. Additional nurses are responsible for collecting important findings related to patient's treatment during examination or observations.

4. Goals

1. To maintain all the relevant documents of the patient which can be helpful while patient's treatment process.

5. Competence

1. Additional nurses need to have cultural competence [32] (Language Level: Swedish, English etc), Educational competence [32] (Bachelor in Nursing: (BSN, BNurs, BScN, BSc, MN)) and work_Experience competence [32] (2-3 years depending on speciality) for collecting important finding related to patient's treatment during examination or observations.

6. Resources

For the achievement of the task, there are certain resources are utilized for performing above activities.

1. Additional nurses need to use notes as resource for gathering important findings.
2. Additional nurses are also used laboratory reports and medical equipments for finding the current patient's illness status.

Figure -18 Activity-Role Model: Collection of Patient Medical Portfolio

Figure –19 Collection of Patient Medical portfolio Process

4.10. Ward Round Process (WRP)

In ward-round process (WRP), it is important to designate a hospital personnel team: Consultant, Senior practitioner, Junior practitioner, nurse person, occupational therapist who they are responsible to manage different tasks: Patient should discharge or retain, Patient's treatment planning and evaluation, Multi-professional Training in ward-round process. These tasks can be achieved through some activities as input in ward-round process.

Designated team 2:

These groups of personnel are used to take ward-round process (WRP) activities as follows:

- Consultant
- Senior practitioner
- Junior practitioner
- Occupational Therapist
- Nurse

The description of the designated team2 can be seen in the figure-20 and figure-20 respectively.

1. Tasks

1. Patient should discharge or retain.

2. Activities

There are the certain activities which helpful for achieving the above task.

1. To review the key features [35][36] of the patient's history.
2. To complete the physical examination of the patient current illness status during ward-round process.
3. To construct the management plan [37] to assess the current situation of patient illness.
4. To present the patient's information to give overview to understand family inherited diseases.
5. To support interactive environment to avoid patient's distressing while examination in ward round.
6. To prepare patient's treatment notes by using SOAP approach [5] in ward-round process.
7. To take consensus, If the hospital personnel are unanimous agreed upon either the patient's illness status is shown that he/she should stay in hospital or discharge.
8. To follow the patient's discharge procedure.

3. Roles

1. Consultant's responsibility to manage the ward-round resources: medical staff, equipments, information on demand.
2. Senior physicians attend to the patient during the ward-round process.
3. Junior physicians assist the senior for attending the patient during the ward-round process.
4. Consultant attend the patient to suggest and analyze the current patient's diseases illness and discusses with the other team members for discharge or retain the patient.
5. Nurses play active role in the wardround to provide relevant patient's history or record keeping.
6. Nurse are responsible to confirm the current status of the reports are completed and add any other information from the previous shift not already recorded [31].
7. Nurses are responsible to manage patient record history from the COSMIC.
8. Head nurse gets the bed availability status from the EBBA.
9. The responsibilities of Occupational therapist are review medication, mental state of patient, risks factors in certain situations and necessary arrangement in the ward round [31].

4. Goals

1. To achieve quality patient's treatment process in the ward-round
 - a. To improve communication among medical professionals to understand each other and learn different skills from each others experiences during the ward-round.
 - b. To focus on patient's concern prior problems or complaints.
 - c. To suggest best optimal management plan to assess the current situation of patient illness status.
 - d. To create friendly atmosphere where multidisciplinary personnel can cooperate to make team for assigning role distribution.
 - e. To provide easeness to the patient so that patient can be a part of patient's decision making for treatment.
 - f. To provide patient's information according the SOAP [5] standard for effective patient's treatment in the ward-round.

5. Competence

1. The consultant has work_Experience competence [32] (8-10 years depending on speciality), Language competence [32] (Swedish, English etc.) and Educational competence [32] (MBBS, MBChB, BMed, Dr.med [70]) to manage the ward-round resources: medical staff, equipments, information on demand.

2. Senior practitioners need Language competence [32] (Language: Swedish, English) and Educational competence [32] (MD; MDCM, Cand.med, DO [70]), work_Experience competence [32](5-6 years) to attend the patient for medical attentions.
3. Junior practitioners need Language competence [32] (Language: Swedish, English) and Educational competence [32] (MD; MDCM, Cand.med [70]), work_Experience competence [32](2-3 years) to assist the senior practitioners.
4. Nurse has Language competence [32] (Language Level: Swedish, English etc), Educational competence [32] (Bachelor in Nursing: (BSN, BNurs, BScN, BSc, MN)) and work_Experience competence [32] (2-3 years depending on speciality).
5. Occupational therapists have Language competence [32] (Language Level: Swedish, English etc), Educational competence [32] (MSOT, MAOT, MOT, OTD, Dr.OT [70]) and work_Experience competence [32] (5-6 years depending on speciality) to review medication, mental state of patient, risks factors in certain situations and necessary arrangement in the ward round [31].

6. Resources

For the achievement of the task, there are certain resources are utilized for performing above activities.

1. Medical staff: Consultant, Senior practitioner, Additional nurses and Junior practitioner as resources are involved to update patient list who are under consideration for treatment.
2. Hospital resources: particular medical ward is used for ward-round.
3. Information systems: COSMIC, EBBA are used for acquiring the suitable information related to patient in the patient's treatment process.
4. Database System: Laboratory database is used to send the patient medical tests reports to nurses to forward in ward-round.
5. Patient medical history is used as reference in the ward-round for patient's treatment.
6. Writing notes is used for post ward-round assessment by junior practitioner and medical students.
7. Patient medical reports for the assessment in the ward-round.

Realization of Ward-round

Figure -20 Activity-Role Model: Patient should Discharge or Retain

Realization of Ward-round

Figure -21 Patient should Discharge or Retain process

1. Tasks

The description of the designated team 1 can be seen in the figure-23 and figure-24 respectively.

2. Patient Treatment Planning Process

2. Activities

There are the certain activities which helpful for achieving the above task.

1. To consider good differential diagnosis [71] in patient's treatment planning while word-round [71].
2. To formulate differential diagnosis involves review of patient's history and clinical examination findings in patient's treatment planning while word-round [71].
3. To identify medical problems and list down them that mention range the patient's illness and helps to construct management plan to tackle the diseases while ward-round [71].
4. To ask additional questions to clarify different aspects of history regarding medicine, effects of medicine, sensitive nature history about *psychiatric and sexual* [71] history, evaluate risk factors related consequences, family history and social history [71].
5. To decide patient's treatment plan according to the patient's illness either *immediate plan* [71] or *long term* [71].

2.1. Immediate Treatment Plan

1. To differentiate patient's treatment situation, it is emergency situation, acute cases, chronic illness or acute deterioration [71].
2. To select the right place according to your experience and observations that where patient feels better for treatment process [71].
3. To follow the standard medical agenda of diagnosis through systematic inquiries about patient's symptoms and medical history which is known as *Disease centred* [72].
4. To provide immediate treatment on the basis of clinical presentation without waiting for the investigation's result [71].
5. To give always priority to be ensured that patient is stable and may require some immediate medical involvement [71].
6. It is very necessary to the multidisciplinary professional to prioritize their investigations according to the urgency of the investigation [71].

2.2. Long Term Treatment Plan

1. In long term, multidisciplinary team members should give participation in the patient's treatment plan according to their expertise in the ward-round [71].

2. For the promotion of good patient's treatment practices, it is necessary to educate about patient's education and training in the patient's treatment planning while ward-round to get optimal results [71].
3. To follow the patient's agenda, including listening and allowing patient's to explain all the reasons for attending, feelings, and expectations for decision making in quality treatment planning [72].
4. To conduct single psychological intervention session during the long term treatment plan with the patients for future prognosis.

3. Roles

1. Consultant responsibility is to identify all possible causes after review the patient's history in patient treatment planning while ward-round.
2. Consultant has also responsibility to identify medical problems and list down them that mention range the patient's illness in patient's treatment planning while ward-round.
3. Senior practitioners formulate differential diagnosis after review of patient's history and clinical examination finding.
4. Junior practitioners are responsible to assist senior and collection of the examination finding.
5. Nurses provide patient's related medical reports or patient's portfolio.
6. Junior practitioners have also responsibilities to ask some additional questions to patient support the quality patient's treatment planning.
7. Senior practitioners decide the treatment plan according to the patient's illness either immediate plan or long term plan.

3.1. Roles in Immediate Treatment Plan

1. Senior practitioners decide that it is emergency situation or others related.
2. Senior practitioners help to junior to decide which place is comfortable for acquiring maximum information from patient in patient's treatment planning.
3. Senior suggests the junior practitioners to follow standard medical agenda of diagnosis through systematic inquiries.
4. Junior practitioners motivate to give medical intervention when the patient is in stable position.
5. Consultant advises multidisciplinary professional to decide their priorities for investigation in patient's treatment process while the ward-round.

3.2. Roles in Long Term Treatment Plan

1. Consultant should push the multidisciplinary professional to promote patient's education and training in patient's treatment planning.

2. Senior practitioner should advice to follow patinet's agenda to acquire maximum involment of patient in treatment decision making procedure.
3. Occupational therapist roles is to conduct single session with patient to collect maximum information related to previous histories.

4. Goals

2. To provide quality patient's treatment planning in the ward-round.
 - a. To analyze the actual causes of patient's illness.
 - b. To achieve optimal medical results to support quality management planning while ward-round.
 - c. To prepare relevent questionnaire pool to ask additional question related to the patient's prvious life experiences or history related to medicine, psychiatric, sexual, family and social.
 - d. To achieve effective decision making planning to tackle patient's illness.

4.1. Goals in Immediate Treatment Plan

- a. To decide optimal management plan in immediate treatment planning.
- b. To follow *disease centred* [72] standard medical agenda for diagnosis in patient treatment planning.
- c. To achieve patient involment in the treatment planning during the ward-round.

4.2. Goals in Long Term Treatment Plan

- a. To ensure the involment of the multidisciplinary in the patient's treatment planning.
- b. To get assurity to follow the patient's agenda for acquiring maximum related information to support decision making process in treatment.
- c. To promote patient education and learning during patient's treatment planning while ward-round.

5. Competence

1. The consultant has work_Experience competence [32] (8-10 years depending on speciality), Language competence [32] (Swedish, English etc.) and Educational competence [32] (MBBS, MBchB, BMed, Dr.med [70]) to identify all possible causes after review the patinet's hisotry in patinet treatment planning while ward-round.
2. The consultant has work_Experience competence [32] (8-10 years depending on speciality), Language competence [32] (Swedish, English etc.) and Educational competence [32] (MBBS, MBchB, BMed, Dr.med [70]) to identify identify medical

3. problems and list down them that mention range the patient's illness in patient's treatment planning while ward-round.
3. Senior practitioners need Language competence [32] (Language: Swedish, English) and Educational competence [32] (MD; MDCM, Cand.med, DO [70]), work_Experience competence [32](5-6 years) formulate differential diagnosis after review of patient's history and clinical examination finding.
4. Junior practitioners need Language competence [32] (Language: Swedish, English) and Educational competence [32] (MD; MDCM, Cand.med [70]), work_Experience competence [32](2-3 years) to assist the senior practitioners and collect examination findings.
5. Junior practitioners need Language competence [32] (Language: Swedish, English) and Educational competence [32] (MD; MDCM, Cand.med [70]), work_Experience competence [32](2-3 years) to ask additional questions to the patients to support quality patient's treatment process.
6. Nurse has Language competence [32] (Language Level: Swedish, English etc), Educational competence [32] (Bachelor in Nursing: (BSN, BNurs, BScN, BSc, MN)) and work_Experience competence [32] (2-3 years depending on speciality) provide patient's related medical reports or patient's portfolio
7. Occupational therapists has has Language competence [32] (Language Level: Swedish, English etc), Educational competence [32] (MSOT, MAOT, MOT, OTD, Dr.OT [70]) and work_Experience competence [32] (5-6 years depending on speciality) is to conduct single session with patient to collect maximum information related to previous histories.

6. Resources

For the achievement of the task, there are certain resources are utilized for performing above activities.

1. Medical staff: Consultant, Senior practitioners, Additional nurses and Junior practitioners and occupational therapists as resources are involved in patient treatment planning while ward-round.
2. Hospital resources: particular medical ward is used for ward-round.
3. Information systems: COSMIC, EBBA are used for acquiring the suitable information related to patient in the patient's treatment planning process.
4. Database System: Laboratory database is used to send the patient medical tests reports to nurses to forward patient treatment planning while ward-round.
5. Patient medical history is used as reference in the ward-round for patient's treatment planning.

- 6.** Writing notes is used for post ward-round assessment by junior practitioners and medical students for patient's treatment planning.
- 7.** Patient medical reports are used for the assessment in patient treatment process while ward-round.

Realization of Ward-round

Figure -22 Activity-Role Model: Immediate Treatment Plan

Figure -23 Activity-Role Model: Long Term Treatment Plan

Realization of Ward-round

Figure -24 Patient Treatment Planning process

Designated team 3:

These groups of personnel are used to take ward-round process (WRP) activities as follows:

- Consultant
- Senior practitioner
- Trainee: Medical Student, Junior practitioner, Nurse

1. Tasks

The description of the designated team 1 can be seen in the figure-25 and figure-26 respectively.

3. Medical Training & Learning Opportunity [27].

In healthcare sector, medical training & learning opportunities are classified into two categories: Teaching perspective and Learning perspective in the patient's treatment concern [27]. The medical training and learning opportunities activities have aimed to achieve some goals which support the efficiency of these activities in patient's treatment process. There are certain goals are proposed to support medical training and learning opportunities tasks in the patient's treatment process.

2. Activities

There are the certain activities which helpful for achieving the above task.

1. To analyze the current urgency of medical skills and competences in the field of patient's treatment and for the quality care services in the hospital.
2. To appoint the medical consultant/senior physician by hospital management to educate medical students and trainees during the ward-round.
3. To provide world class facilities to the consultants for motivation to serve medical students and junior medical staff in the hospital.
4. To reserve the resources: conference room, seminar room etc for teaching perspective to educate medical staff for the improvement of the patient's treatment.
5. To analyze the degree of success of patient's treatment and patient management planning [27].
6. To identify relevant teaching and learning material during the patient's treatment teaching session.
7. To introduce some clinical teaching techniques for seminal events [73].
8. To comparing the current patient case study with similar referenced case studies [27].

3. Roles

1. Medical consultant (from multidisciplinary medical field : psychology, nursing and caring, physician, Surgery and occupational thereapy or specialist of any domain) has role to teach medical students for patient's treatment learning while ward-round.
2. Medical consultant advices to senior and junior practitioners while ward-round assessment.
3. Senior practitioner should arrange some seminars to educate junior practitioners, medical students and nurses related to patient's treatment process.
4. Senior practitioner books conference room for teaching session for patient treatment process.
5. Junior practitioner presents the case study of concentering subjects during the teaching session.
6. Medical students prepare writing notes for learning and assessment patient's case study after the ward-round teaching session

4. Goals

These following goals can be traced out from the literature and modeling workshop [27]:

1. To maximize medical educational training and learning opportunities.
 - a. To provide on-the-job training to the junior medical practitioners for patient's treatment process.
 - b. To provide friendly enviornment to maximize trainee's contribution in the ward-round [27].
 - c. To encourage the trainee's opinion on patient diagnosis and treatment management perspective in the patient's treatment procees.
 - d. To entertain current practices to fullfill the patient's treatment gap and emphasize on comparison of current and past case studies.
 - e. To promote some salient features for verbal and non verbal communication skills, observational skills, self awareness and leadership skills through teaching session related to patient's treatment process [73].
 - f. To analyze the degree of success of patient's treatment and treatment planning [27].

5. Competence

1. The consultant has work_Experience competence [32] (8-10 years depending on speciality), Language competence [32] (Swedish, English etc.) and Educational competence [32] (MBBS, MBchB, BMed, Dr.med [70]) to teach medical students for patient's treatment learning while ward-round.

2. Senior practitioners need Language competence [32] (Language: Swedish, English) and Educational competence [32] (MD; MDCM, Cand.med, DO [70]), work_Experience competence [32] (5-6 years) arrange some seminars to educate junior practitioners, medical students and nurses related to patient's treatment process.

6. Resources

For the achievement of the task, there are certain resources are utilized for performing above activities.

1. Medical staff: Consultant, Senior practitioner, as resources are involved in medical teaching and learning opportunities in patient's treatment process.
2. Hospital resources: particular medical ward, conference room are used for patient's treatment teaching concerns.
3. Information systems: COSMIC is used for acquiring the suitable information related to patient in the patient's treatment process for teaching perspective.
4. Nurses are the trainee during the teaching session.
5. Patient medical history is used as reference in the ward-round for patient's treatment teaching.
6. Writing notes is used for post ward-round assessment by junior practitioner and medical students for patient's treatment during teaching session [5].
7. Patient medical case studies are taken during the teaching session for reference to educate current subjective studies.

Realization of Ward-round

Figure -25 Activity-Role Model: Medical Education & Learning Opportunities

Realization of Ward-round

Figure -26 Medical Education & Learning Opportunities process

4.11. Post Ward-round Process (PWRP)

Post ward-round process (PWRP) is held to take some time out with the multidisciplinary team and made discussion some of the tasks have to taken in the patient's treatment process [5]. In post ward-round, where senior practitioners advice to the junior and medical students, what you have seen during the ward-round, what think about the case studies in ward-round session having no too much ambitions [5]. Post ward-round process (PWRP), invites the junior practitioners and medical students to suggest and evaluate the current patient's illness status and attempt to propose optimal solution with strong arguments for quality patient's treatment and junior's learning perspective.

Designated team 4:

These groups of personnel are used to take ware-round process (WRP) activities as follows:

- Senior Practioners
- Junior Practitioners
- Medical Students
- Occupational Therapists

The description of the designated team4 can be seen in the figure-27 and figure-28 respectively.

1. Tasks

1. Group discussion for evaluating current analysis of patient's illness.

2. Activities

There are the certain activities which helpful for achieving the above task.

1. To take time out after the ward-round session with multidisciplinary team to evaluate the curretn patient's illness in post-ward session [5].
2. For junior staff: junior practitioners and medical students need to propose optimal solution with strong arguments to convince seniors for quality patient's treatment process.
3. To improve the communication gaps between the junior participants and senior participants during the post ward-round session.
4. To debating pros and cons of various diagnostic and management options to support quality care for patient's treatment [27].
5. To comapre the cureent case studies with the reference legacy cases for help out in medication's decision making [27].
6. To deciding on the next steps for patient management and evaluate all the treatment options for patinet's treatment process [27].

7. To highlight what are the needs necessary in relation to each patient during treatment [27].

3. Roles

1. Junior staff: Junior practitioners and medical students take participation to evaluate the current patient's illness in post-ward process.
2. Junior staff: Junior practitioners and medical students propose optimal solution with strong arguments to convince seniors for quality patient's treatment process.
3. Medical students are responsible to make comparison between legacy case studies and current case studies related to concerning subject during the post-ward process.
4. Seniors are responsible for taking decision on the next steps or patient management and different treatment options.

4. Goals

These following goals can be traced out from the literature and modeling workshop [27]:

1. To promote quality group discussion for current case study analysis.
 - a. To give promotion to support open discussion among the multidisciplinary professionals in patient's treatment process [27].
 - b. To improve the communication gaps between juniors staff and senior staff for maximum learning and confidence in patient's treatment.
 - c. To take vibrant decisions to get quality health care services for patient's treatment.

5. Competence

1. Senior practitioners need Language competence [32] (Language: Swedish, English) and Educational competence [32] (MD; MDCM, Cand.med, DO [70]), work_Experience competence [32] (5-6 years) responsible for taking decisions on the next steps or patient management and different treatment options.
2. Junior practitioners need Language competence [32] (Language: Swedish, English) and Educational competence [32] (MD; MDCM, Cand.med [70]), work_Experience competence [32] (2-3 years) to take participation to evaluate current patient's illness in post-ward process.
3. Medical students need Language competence [32] (Language: Swedish, English) and Educational competence [32] (MSPAS [70]), work_Experience competence [32] (beginner) are responsible to make comparison between legacy case studies and current case studies related to concerning subject during the post-ward process.

6. Resources

For the achievement of the task, there are certain resources are utilized for performing above activities.

1. Medical staff: Senior practitioners, Junior practitioners and medical students as resources are involved in post ward-round assessment for patient's treatment process.
2. Hospital resources: particular medical ward, conference room are used for post ward-round patient's treatment teaching concerns.
3. Information systems: COSMIC is used for acquiring the suitable information related to patient in the patient's treatment process for teaching perspective.
4. Patient medical history is used as reference in the post ward-round for patient's treatment assessment.
5. Writing notes is used for post ward-round assessment by junior practitioners and medical students for patient's treatment during teaching session [5].
6. Patient medical case studies are taken during the patient's treatment assessment.

Realization of Ward-round

Figure -28 Post Ward-Round Group Discussion Process

4.12. Final Remarks

This chapter explains the realization of modernity ward-round with comparison of traditional ward-round and also realizes to achieve the objective of ward-round in this thesis work. This chapter also projects the need of admission procedure (AP) before going into the detail of ward-round processes because the admission procedure criteria helps to medical practitioners to take vibrant decisions for patient treatment planning either in short term planning or in long term planning during ward-round session.

This chapter also highlights competence selection criteria. This competence criteria is necessary of medical practitioner's roles for performing different tasks during the ward-round session. This chapter tells about conceptual model which gives pictorial interpretation of modeling workshop's working flow in figure-12. This chapter also explains the ward-round processes in terms of Pre Ward-round process (PRWP), Ward-round process (WRP) and Post Ward-round process (PWRP). Each ward-round process has different designated team members, contain different tasks, certain activities which are involve achieving these tasks, different individual's roles, defining goals which want to achieve during research work and define certain competence level of hospital's personnel according to their assign roles.

This chapter also includes process modeling of these activities in ward-round session which has explained in figure-15 and so forth.

5. Results

In this chapter, I have explained and concluded the results in the form of ontology models and presented in the form of ontology development. I have perceived the required information from the modelling workshop from the domain's experts and reviewed relevant literature to get sufficient knowledge about domain's problem. I have conducted the research in a systematic way by using Mixed Method Design Process which is combination of action Research and Constructive research. I have chosen Hybrid Methodology which is composed of Methontology and Tove methodology for the implementation of models in an ontology language OWL. For development point of view, I have used Protégé 4.0.2 version. During my research work, I have made discussion with my knowledge mentor and domain experts and also presented my work in workshops for necessary improvement.

I have developed a basic model that interprets the actual working of domain's scenario which will be implemented in ontology based environment like Protégé tool. To construct the different models is the technique to present different concepts into pictorial form and define the relations between them.

5.1. Modelling Workshops

I have arranged modelling workshops with domain experts to ensure the quality of work and the applicability of models during my research. I have discussed my research work with domain experts to validate the results.

5.1.1. Modelling Workshop (I)

I have been conducted modelling workshop in the start of thesis writing. The purpose of this workshop is to present the work to the experts to validate it and take some good suggestions for further improvements in the models of ontology for implementation's concern.

5.1.2. Modelling Workshop (II)

The second modelling workshop had been held in the middle of my work at the end of design phase. The purpose of this modelling workshop was to present final version of ontology design to the domain experts to get specific detailed information about the domain. In this modelling workshop, I have discussed different design issues, different individual's roles in the ward-round, different resources that has been used in ward-round session, also mentioned the key responsibilities of the intended users of these resources. In this modelling session, I have focused different individual's roles like consultant, senior practitioner, junior practitioner, additional nurse, head nurse, occupational therapist and laboratory personal in Ryhov Hospital Jonkoping.

5.1.3. Ontology Reuse

I have already mentioned about the ontology reuse in section 2.8 about different ways of reusing ontologies in the ontology that is being used in my research work. I have taken some good examples which are quite suitable for reusing ontologies from the Vladimir Tarasov, Kurt Sandkuhl, Magnus Lundqvist [32]. I have reused different concepts from literature [32] general competence, cultural competence, occupational competence and competence proficiency level. I have used core concepts of competence in my ontology development.

5.2. Proposed Ontology based Model for Ward-round

I have proposed ontology based model for ward-round which describes different entities involved in it and also defined the relations between them for readers' understanding. This proposed ontology based model supports in the ward-round (decision making procedure) phenomenon [3]. This proposed ontology modelling can be solution to address information flow problem in ward-round hospital unit.

5.3. High Level Ontology Based Mode for Ward-round

Figure -29 High Level Ontology Based Model for Ward-round

The high level ontology based model in figure-29 describes the working flow and functionality of basic model for ward-round. The components and different entities of this model are followed [3]:

1. Medical Staff
2. Role
3. Process
4. Resources
5. Organization
6. Competence
7. Competence Selection Criteria
8. Goals
9. Tasks
10. Activities

The medical staff members are involved in different processes (Pre Ward-round, Ward-round, and Post Ward-round) according to their competences and assigned roles [3]. The role's assignment by the consultant or senior practitioner in the current basic model is decided that which process is initiated. The selection of the processes is followed by the medical agenda [72] in the patient treatment procedure. Different processes in the propose model are utilized different resources for finding related information from the different information channels according to the set rules which are defined by specific organization (Hospital Management) [3].

These processes must have certain goals and every goal has certain tasks that follow certain activities to lead these goals. This competence's selection is carried out from the competence selection criteria. "Component selection criteria" is the component that is used in the basic model which filters and support for the selection of right person's information according to his/her competences and skills so that he/she can perform his/her responsibilities against his/her roles.

5.4. Detail Ontology based Model for Ward-round

In above section 5.2., the main task is to draw ontology based model in detail so that reader can easily understand the working flow among the different involved entities in the basic model. As in the figure-30, we can visualize that Medical members (Consultant, Senior practitioners, Junior practitioners, Nurse: Head Nurse, Additional Nurse, Occupational Therapist) have different assigned roles in the patient's treatment process.

This model is highlighting three major competences which are used by medical members for performing different tasks in Ward-round patient's treatment process. Different roles utilize different resources (Medical ward, EBBA, COSMIC and Laboratory database) and are responsible to initiate processes (Pre ward-round, Ward-round, Post Ward-round

processes) which contains different tasks and activities to achieve different set goals for achieving quality patient treatment procedure during the ward-round.

The main focus of this ontology based model during ward round in healthcare unit is to share relevant information for patient's treatment that supports decision making process. The usage of ontology based modeling is used to support certain activities of each task in the ward-round which address ward-round information flow problems in healthcare. To support research focus section (1.2.1), one way is to identify the information need of individuals and mention competence profile, second is to identify their roles in different tasks, third is to find certain activities which are followed in different tasks [3].

To understand the current situation in the Ryhov, hospital, Jönköping, we have arranged workshops and discussions with the domain experts during our work to check the validity and practical implementation of our proposed model [3].

In the beginning of the work, we have taken first workshop with experts; the agenda of the workshop is to describe the current problems of ward-round in Ryhov, hospital and made understanding notes of the whole discussion during workshop. We have drawn initial models to address the current problems in the ward-round and presented to the experts for evaluation and received some comments after their assessment, and then we have updated it according to their instructions [3].

Figure-30 “Detail Ontology based Model for Ward-round”

5.5. Medical Staff

Figure-31 Medical Staff

As in figure-31, there are group of people: patient, medical student, medical staff etc. are engaged with different hospital’s activities. The classification of the medical staff is shown according to the discussion. These personnel are involved in ward-round (decision making procedure) to initiate different ward-round processes according to their roles and competencies. We have defined certain key participants in medical staff from modeling workshop and observations like: Consultant, Medical Practitioner: Senior Medical Practitioner, Junior Practitioner, and Medical Nurse: Additional Nurse, Head Nurse, Medical Occupational Therapist and Lab-coordinator.

5.6. Role

Here in figure-32, that is the abstraction of few roles which are involved? These roles are related to multidisciplinary professional participants in the ward-round patient treatment process. These roles are categorized according to the nature of role with competences and skills of professionals. The categories of professionals roles in patient treatment process are as follows: Practitioner Role: Surgeon Practitioner Role, General Practitioner Role, Specialist Practitioner Role, Nurse Role: Additional Nurse Role, Head Nurse Role, Occupational Therapist Role: Senior and Junior Occupational Therapist Role, Lab Coordinator Role, Medical Student Role and Medical Administrator Role.

5.7. Organization

Figure- 33 Organization

There are main types of organization in healthcare which are shown in figure-33. In our thesis, the mostly concentration is on hospital and rest of the organization's types are out of the focus. Every hospital has different wards and every ward is dedicated for particular department in the healthcare.

In the figure-34, there are different types of resources are utilized in the current discussion of ward-round in patient treatment process. The resource is generally categorized into two category information resource and physical resource. The information resource: information system, patient medical history, patient's concern status report are useful for acquiring the maximum information related to patient's treatment and other resources support in ward-round patient's treatment procedure. These resources are categorized for reader's understanding.

1. Patient Medical History

Patient medical history is the most important feature in the patient's treatment procedure because it is one kind of resource which provides detail information about patient's illness status, and observations which hospital personal perceive during his/her stay in hospital.

2. Information System

Information system is quite helpful for the disseminated the information among multidisciplinary team and organization so information system: EBBA, COSMIC, Laboratory Database are also very important in the patient's treatment for acquiring patient's record information from the COSMIC (Electronic Patient Record System) and finding the patient-admission information status from EBBA (Patient-admission Status System) in Ryhov, Jönköping, Sweden.

3. Medical Ward

Medical ward is the main resource in the ward-round patient's treatment process because here we can perform ward-round activities for achieving quality patient's treatment in ward-round.

4. Patient's Concern Report

Patient's concern reports are very important resource to evaluate and assess the patient's current status of illness. Patient's concern reports are consist of patient's history status report, medical staff availability status report for ward-round processes, ward bed availability status report and information systems status report for patient treatment process in healthcare.

5. Medical Note

Medical Note writing is very critical for preparing the patient's history report before going into the ward-round process. It has importance for medical students to write some key features about the whole assessment during the ward-round for learning point of view so that they can make patient's treatment plan for future perspective.

6. Physical Resource

Hospital physical resources are concerned with education learning opportunity resources like seminar, conference room for medical students learning point of view and also related the physical resources which are utilized in the patient's treatment process like medical wards.

5.9. Competence

Figure- 35 Competence

According to the literature review [32], we have been found three main categories of competences involved in the basic discussion of ward-round process. These competences are General competence, Occupational competence, and Cultural competence in the figure-35. These competencies are very essential for the selection of the right person for the right situation in the patient's treatment process. Competence also supports in competence selection criteria for individual's selection. These major competences are further divided for reader's understanding into Work _experience and Educational competence and cultural competence.

5.10.Process

Figure -36 Process

In the figure -36, we describe three types of the main processes which are involved in different stages of patient's treatment. These processes are pre ward-round process, ward-round process and post ward-round process.

5.11.Goals

Goals are basically projected the image of desired state that needs to be achieved. In the discussion of ward-round patient treatment process, we have been focused on some goals that may be contributed in quality patient's treatment procedure in healthcare.

1. To achieve quality patient's treatment management plan in ward-round process.
 - 1.1. The patient's medical results in patient treatment process should be verified by relevant resource personnel.
 - 1.2. The patient's medical results should be received timely due to smooth working flow among different information channels for patient's treatment process.
2. To notify the seniors about patient's overall condition is improving or deteriorating.
 - 2.1. To create interaction with the patient to avoid distressing while investigation.
3. To maintain all the relevant documents of the patient which can be helpful while patient's treatment examination or observations.
4. To achieve quality patient's treatment process in the ward-round
 - 4.1. To provide easiness to the patient so that patient can be a part of patient's decision making for treatment.
 - 4.2. To improve communication among medical professionals to understand each other for skills and experiences learning.
 - 4.3. To focus on patient's concern prior problems or complaints.
 - 4.4. To suggest best optimal management plan to assess the current situation of patient illness status.
 - 4.5. To create friendly atmosphere where multidisciplinary personnel can cooperate to make team for assigning role distribution.
 - 4.6. To provide patient's information according the SOAP standard for effective patient's treatment in the ward-round.
5. To provide quality patient's treatment planning in the ward-round (Long Term Plan).
 - 5.1. To analyze the actual causes of patient's illness.

- 5.2. To achieve optimal medical results to support quality management planning while ward-round.
- 5.3. To prepare relevant questionnaire pool to ask additional questions related to the patient's previous life experiences or history or medicine, psychiatric, sexual, family and social.
- 5.4. To achieve effective decision making planning to tackle patient's illness.
- 5.5. To ensure the involvement of the multidisciplinary in the patient's treatment planning.
- 5.6. To get assurance to follow the patient's agenda for acquiring maximum related information to support treatment decision making process.
- 5.7. To promote patient education and learning during patient's treatment planning while ward-round.

5.8. Immediate Patient Treatment Plan

- 5.8.1. To decide optimal plan in immediate treatment planning.
 - 5.8.2. To follow disease centred, standard medical agenda for diagnosis in patient treatment planning.
 - 5.8.3. To achieve patient involvement in the treatment planning during the ward-round.
6. To maximize medical educational training and learning opportunities.
 - 6.1. To provide on-the-job training to the junior medical practitioners for patient's treatment process.
 - 6.2. To encourage the trainee's opinion on patient diagnosis and treatment management perspective in the patient's treatment process.
 - 6.3. To entertain current practices to fulfill the patient's treatment gap and emphasize on comparison of current and past case studies.
 - 6.4. To promote some salient features verbal and non verbal communication skills, observational skills, self awareness and leadership skills through teaching
 - 6.5. To analyze the degree of success of patient's treatment and treatment planning.
 - 6.6. To promote quality group discussion for current case study analysis.
 - 6.7. To give promotion to support open discussion among the multidisciplinary professional in patient's treatment process.
 - 6.8. To improve the communication gaps between juniors staff and senior staff for maximum learning and confidence in patient's treatment.
 - 6.9. To take vibrant decisions to get quality health care services for patient's treatment.

5.12. Activities

Figure-37 Activities

Activity is basically described the action which we take in different tasks during the ward-round patient treatment processes. Here in figure-37, we have three major Activities, and every process has own activities in different tasks respectively.

5.13. Main Scenario Modelling

In the following part of the report, we would like to give ontology based modeling examples which will describe the domain scenario of ward-round and involved participants and how they perform different tasks and activities to achieve certain goals for quality patient's treatment in Ryhov, Jönköping healthcare unit in Sweden.

In figure-38, we can observe main scenario that particular team has different assigned role with different competences and performing different tasks and activities which lead to achieve certain set goals in the main scenario of ward-round in cardiology department of Ryhov, hospital, Jönköping, Sweden.

For understanding of reader, we have taken some examples in figure-39 and figure-40, where we can observe the working pattern of Additional Nurse Role and Junior Practitioner Role in the following discussion.

Example Statement: Additional Nurse Role is assigned to Susanne Ålgren who is working in Ryhov, Hospital, Jönköping and has some competences to perform different tasks and certain activities in pre and post ward-round process. Here, some main responsibilities are to utilize hospital resources (COSMIC) to take patient record and prepare patient medical history report for ward-round session and also maintain the particular Ward in figure-39.

Example Statement: Junior Practitioner Role is assigned to Ander Bill who is working in Ryhov, Hospital, Jönköping and has some competences to perform different tasks and certain activities like: To complete the physical examination of the patient in pre and post ward-round process. Her main responsibilities are to visit particular ward daily and prepare patient medical history report to inform senior to call for ward-round session and also maintain the particular Ward in figure-40.

Results

Figure-38 "Main Scenario Modelling"

Results

Note: Detail description of Additional Nurse Role in Appendix section 8.10.

Figure-39 Additional Nurse Role

Results

Note: Detail description of Junior Practitioner Role in Appendix section 8.10.

Figure-40 Junior Practitioner Role

5.14. Implementation of Ontology Model/Results

One of the promising tasks is to develop Ontology based model in this thesis's work which will represent all basic concepts of ward-round in healthcare unit. This model is developed by using Ontology editor, Protégé 4 to build OWL Ontologies. We have implemented our proposed model into ontology based environment to show knowledge about the same domain of interest (Ward-round, Healthcare).

The numbers of classes are used in the ontology model which covers the main discussion about ward-round in healthcare. The classes have hierarchy structure which starts from root class: THING of Protégé 4.0.2 in the figure-41. The above figure describes 18 main classes and their hierarchal structure.

For realization of ontology based model in the figure-42, we have focused on designated team which consists of different person's roles, they are working in particular ward of particular department (Cardiology) and performing different activities, tasks and achieve certain goals during the ward-round processes.

Figure-42 Image of Designated Team Class

In the following discussion in figure-43, Medical Member class contains different personnel like Medical Administrator, Medical Practitioner, Medical Nurse, Medical Occupational Therapist and Medical Lab Coordinator they are very important participants in the ward-round ontology based model.

Figure-43 Image of Medical Member Class

So, I would like to explain the working example of Medical Nurse Role and Medical Male Practitioner Role which belong to some organization that is Ryhov, hospital, Jönköping for understanding in figure-44. Medical Nurse Role is classified into Additional Nurse Role and Head Nurse Role and Medical Practitioner which is classified into Child Specialist Practitioner Role and General Practitioner Role and Surgeon Practitioner Role, performing different assigned roles. Every individual has distinct role, competences, performed different tasks, participates in different activities and initiates different ward-round process.

The figure displays three screenshots of a software interface showing role hierarchies and their associated properties. Each screenshot consists of a tree view on the left and a list of properties on the right.

Top Screenshot: MedicalNurseRole

- Tree View:
 - Person
 - Process
 - Resource
 - Role
 - LabCoordinatorRole
 - MedicalAdministratorRole
 - MedicalNurseRole
 - AdditionalNurseRole
 - HeadNurseRole
 - MedicalPractitionerRole
 - OccupationalTherapistRole
 - PatientRole

- Properties:
- MedicalNurseRole
- hasGeneralCompetence **some** GeneralCompetence
- hasEducationalField **value** Nursing
- hasEducationalCompetence **min 1** EducationalCompetence
- hasWorkExperience **min 2** WorkExperienceCompetence
- speakLanguage **min 1** Language
- visitWardDaily **min 1** MedicalWard
- Inferred anonymous superclasses:
 - hasCompetence **some** Competence
 - isAssignRole **min 1** Person

Middle Screenshot: HeadNurseRole

- Tree View:
 - PatientTreatmentPlan
 - Person
 - Process
 - Resource
 - Role
 - LabCoordinatorRole
 - MedicalAdministratorRole
 - MedicalNurseRole
 - AdditionalNurseRole
 - HeadNurseRole
 - MedicalPractitionerRole
 - OccupationalTherapistRole
- Properties:
 - MedicalNurseRole
 - hasGeneralCompetence **some** GeneralCompetence
 - hasEducationalField **value** Nursing
 - hasWorkExperience **min 5** WorkExperienceCompetence
 - speakLanguage **min 1** Language
 - visitWardDaily **min 1** MedicalWard
 - Inferred anonymous superclasses:
 - hasCompetence **some** Competence

Bottom Screenshot: SurgeonPractitionerRole

- Tree View:
 - MedicalAdministratorRole
 - MedicalNurseRole
 - AdditionalNurseRole
 - HeadNurseRole
 - MedicalPractitionerRole
 - ChildSpecialistPractitionerRole
 - GeneralPractitionerRole
 - SurgeonPractitionerRole
 - ConsultantRole
 - OccupationalTherapistRole
 - PatientRole
 - Rule
- Properties:
 - SurgeonPractitionerRole
 - hasGeneralCompetence **some** GeneralCompetence
 - hasEducationalField **value** Cardiology
 - hasEducationalCompetence **min 1** EducationalCompetence
 - hasWorkExperience **min 8** WorkExperienceCompetence
 - speakLanguage **min 2** Language
 - Inferred anonymous superclasses:
 - hasCompetence **some** Competence

Figure-44 Image of Medical Nurse Role & Medical Practitioner Role

As in figure-45, different processes: Pre Ward-round Process, Ward-round Process and Post-Ward-round Process are intimated by person's roles with different skills and utilize different resources of Hospital which are EBBA, COSMIC, Laboratory Database and Medical Ward of Cardiology department in Ryhov Hospital, Jönköping, Sweden according to the treatment requirements. In Pre Ward-round Process, the designated team1 which consist of medical members like Medical Nurse, Junior Practitioner and Occupational Therapist to perform pre ward-round activities to support Ward-round process. In Ward-round Process, designated team2 and designated team3 are involved for patient treatment decision making and for the construct of treatment plan. In Post Ward-round process, designated team 4 is involved for the analytical discussion and evaluation of current situation of the patient in Ward-round process.

Figure- 45 Image of Ward-round Process

5.14.1. Domain Classes and Properties

Main Class	Disjoint Class	Main Class	Disjoint Class
THING	Activity	Activity	Pre Ward-round Activity
	City		Ward-round Activity
	Competence		Post Ward-round Activity
	Country	Competence	Cultural Competence
	Department		General Competence
	Designated Team		Occupational Competence
	Disease	Educational Field	Medicine
	Goal		Nursing And Caring
	Language		Surgery
	Medical Ward		
Organization	Occupational Group	General Practitioner Group	
Patient Admission Criteria		Medical Specialist Group	
Patient Treatment Plan		Nursing Professional Group	
Person			
Process			
Role			
Rule	Occupational Competence	Work Experience	
Task		Competence	
			Educational Competence

Results

		Disease	Acute Disease Chronic Disease Skin Disease
		Medical Ward	Emergency Medical Ward General Medical Ward Private Medical Ward
Goal	Pre Ward-round Goal Ward-round Goal Post Ward-round Goal		
		Organization	County Council Hospital Pharmaceutical Company
Patient Treatment Process	Long Term Treatment Short Term Treatment		
Personal Ability	Planning And Designing Ability Support And Guidance Ability Problem Solving Ability	Patient Admission Criteria	Emergency Patient Criteria Routinewise Patient Criteria
		Cultural Competence	Intercultural Sensitivity Language Competence
Competence Proficiency Level	Educational level Experience Level General Competence Level Language Level Skill Level Intercultural Sensitivity Level	Specialist Area Competence	Acute Disease Specialist Blood Disease Specialist Heart Disease Specialist Skin Disease Specialist Viral Disease Specialist
Hospital Department	Administration Depart. Emergency Department General Department	Medical Member	Medical Administrator Medical Lab Coordinator Medical Nurse Medical Occupational Therapist. Medical Practitioner
Person	Patient Medical Student		
Medical Nurse	Female Nurse Male Nurse	Medical Practitioner	Male Practitioner Female Practitioner

Process	Pre Ward-round Process Ward-round Process Post Ward-round Process	Medical Occupational Therapist	Male Occupational Therapist Female Occupational Therapist
		Resource	Information Resource Physical Resource
Task	Pre Ward-round Task Ward-round Task Post Ward-round Task	Role	Lab Coordinator Role Medical Administrator Role Medical Nurse Role Medical Practitioner Role Occupational Therapist Role
IS Resource	Laboratory Database Patient Admit IS Patient Record IS		

Table-2: Domain Classes and Disjoint Classes Hierarchy

5.14.2. OWL Property Axioms

Axiom	Property	Class	Cardinality
Transitive	ObjectProperty(sendMedicalReport Transitive)	Role, Role	sendMedicalReport (min..1 or max..*)
Asymmetric	ObjectProperty(hasTeam Asymmetric)	Person, DesignatedTeam	hasTeam (min..1 or max..*)

Axiom	Property	Class	Cardinality
Inverse Of	ObjectProperty(hasCompetence inverseOf(isCompetenceOf))	Competence, Role	isCompetenceOf (min..1 or max..*)
	ObjectProperty(hasRole inverseOf(isRoleOf))	Role, Designated Team	IsRoleOf (min..1 or max..*)
	ObjectProperty(hasRole inverseOf(isAssignedRoleTo))	Role, Designated Team	isAssignedRoleTo (min..1 or max..*)

Table-3 Axiom Properties

5.14.3. Promising Role in Healthcare Business

Health care business is mainly based on hospital organization in which different personal have different roles. These roles are assigned according to their competence, skills, experience and social influence in the organization. In our discussion, we consider different personal like Ander Bill, Inger Johansson, Yvonee Truesson having promising roles junior, senior practitioner and consultant in the Ryhov, Hospital, Jönköping, Sweden. They people work in the city Jönköping, Sweden and performing their duties in special medical ward (Emergency, General, and Private) of cardiology department of Ryhov, Hospital.

Figure-46 Image of Senior Practitioner Role and Consultant Role

These above two roles in figure-46 are related to designated team2 who perform different activities, Tasks related to medical training and learning opportunity and take decision either patient should discharge or retain for further treatment during the ward-round session. The other designated team2 is consist of Medical nurse Susanna Ålgren as a Additional Nurse and other is Fridella Gunilla as a Head Nurse and Ander Bill as Junior Practitioner. Susanna Ålgren is certified nurse and her responsibilities are to get patient record from COSMIC information system and collect the patient medical results status report from the laboratory database and inform to the senior practitioners about patient current illness status. Fridella Gunilla is also certified head nurse and her responsibilities are to check the bed availability status from EBBA information system and prepare patient medical history for ward-round treatment session. Ander Bill is certified junior practitioner to perform duties to visit the particular ward daily and complete physical examination of patient and call ward-round meeting to inform senior in Ryhov, hospital in Jönköping, Sweden in following figure-47, figure-48, figure-49 respectively.

Results

Object properties: hasJuniorPractitionerRole

- hasProcess
- hasResource
- hasRole
 - hasAdditionalNurseRole
 - hasConsultantRole
 - hasHeadNurseRole
 - hasJuniorPractitionerRole
 - hasOccupationalTherapistRole
 - hasSeniorPractitionerRole
- hasTask
- initiateProcess

Property values:

- isAssignedRoleTo Ander_Bill
- initiatePreWardroundProcess PreWardroundProcess1
- hasEducationalField Cardiology
- generalCompetenceLevel generalCompetence-StrongLevel
- hasWorkExperience 2-3_Years
- hasCountry Sweden
- manageGeneralWard CardiologyGeneralWard
- LanguageCompetenceLevel LanguageCompetence-StrongLevel
- participatePreWardroundActivity Activity3:ToPrepareCriticalMedicalHisotryOfCertainDisease
- visitWardDaily CardiologyGeneralWard
- getPatientRecordStatus COSMIC
- presentCaseStudy PatientMedicalCaseStudy
- hasEducationalCompetence MD,MDCM,Cand.med
- hasLanguageCompetence Swedish
- acheiveGoal Goal1:ToAcheiveEffectiveDecisionMaking
- PerformPreWardroundPTask Task5:ToGetSatisfactionOfThePatient'sMedicalResults
- workAt RyhovHospital

Figure-47 Image of Junior Practitioner Role

Object properties: hasAdditionalNurseRole

- hasProcess
- hasResource
- hasRole
 - hasAdditionalNurseRole
 - hasConsultantRole
 - hasHeadNurseRole
 - hasJuniorPractitionerRole
 - hasOccupationalTherapistRole
 - hasSeniorPractitionerRole
- hasTask
- initiateProcess
- isActivityOf
- isAssignedRoleTo
- isCompetenceOf
- isProcessOf
- isTaskOf
- madeTeam
- manageTeachingResource

Property values:

- hasEducationalField Nursing
- workAt RyhovHospital
- hasWorkExperience 2-3_Years
- getPatientRecordStatus COSMIC
- hasLanguageCompetence Swedish
- performWardroundTask Task3:PatientTreatmentPlanningProcess
- LanguageCompetenceLevel LanguageCompetence-StrongLevel
- initiateWardroundProcess WardroundProcess1
- followAdmissionProcess RoutinewisePatientAdmissionCriteria1
- acheiveGoal Goal1:ToAcheiveEffectiveDecisionMaking
- hasPrepare PatientHistoryStatusReport1
- participateWardroundActivity Activity2:ToPreparePatient'sTreatmentNotesUsingSOAPApproach
- participatePreWardroundActivity Activity1:ToCollectPatientRelatedDocuments
- visitWardDaily CardiologyGeneralWard
- hasCountry Sweden
- hasEducationalCompetence BSN,_BNurs,_BSc,_MN
- generalCompetenceLevel generalCompetence-StrongLevel
- getMedicalTestReportStatus LabortaryDatabase
- PerformPreWardroundPTask Task1:CollectionOfPatientMedicalPortfolio
- hasGeneralCompetence AbilityToHandleSituation-StrongLevel
- initiatePreWardroundProcess PreWardroundProcess1
- isAssignedRoleTo Susanna_Ålgren
- manageGeneralWard CardiologyGeneralWard

Figure-48 Image of Additional Nurse Role

Object properties: hasHeadNurseRole

- hasGeneralCompetence
- hasOccupationalCompetence
- hasCompetenceLevel
- hasCountry
- hasDisease
- hasHospitalLocation
- hasPrepare
- hasProcess
- hasResource
- hasRole
 - hasAdditionalNurseRole
 - hasConsultantRole
 - hasHeadNurseRole
 - hasJuniorPractitionerRole
 - hasOccupationalTherapistRole
 - hasSeniorPractitionerRole

Property values:

- manageEmergencyWard CardiologyEmergencyWard
- hasLanguageCompetence Swedish
- LanguageCompetenceLevel LanguageCompetence-StrongLevel
- acheiveGoal Goal1:ToAcheiveEffectiveDecisionMaking
- hasGeneralCompetence generalCompetence-StrongLevel
- participatePreWardroundActivity Activity1:ToCollectPatientRelatedDocuments
- participatePreWardroundActivity PreWardroundProcess1
- workAt RyhovHospital
- hasEducationalField Nursing
- PerformPreWardroundPTask Task4:UpdatePatientList
- isAssignedRoleTo Fridella_Gunilla
- PerformPreWardroundPTask Task1:CollectionOfPatientMedicalPortfolio
- performWardroundTask Task3:PatientTreatmentPlanningProcess
- hasEducationalCompetence BSN,_BNurs,_BSc,_MN
- getWardbedAvailabilityStatus EBBA
- performWardroundTask Task2:PatientShouldDischargeOrRetain
- participateWardroundActivity Activity2:ToPreparePatient'sTreatmentNotesUsingSOAPApproach
- hasCountry Sweden
- visitWardDaily CardiologyEmergencyWard
- initiateWardroundProcess WardroundProcess1
- hasWorkExperience 5-6_Years

Figure- 49 Image of Head Nurse Role

5.14.4. Implementation of Main Scenario Modelling

A designated team which consists of medical members and they have distinct roles which utilize different resources: COSMIC, EBBA and laboratory database and medical ward to initiate certain processes, tasks and activities to achieve set goals in particular ward-round scenario in figure-50.

Designated team has different instances of team like designated team2. For example, designated team2 perform certain task: Task1: Collection of patient medical portfolio, Task2: Patient should discharge or retain, Task3: Patient treatment planning process. Designated team2 initiate certain processes: Pre-Ward-round Process1 and Ward-round Process1 and participate in different certain activities: Activity1: To collect patient related documents or medical notes, Activity2: To prepare patient's treatment notes using SOAP approach [5], Activity3: To take time out after the ward-round process to evaluate the current patient's illness. Each role has certain competences and competence proficiency levels. Medical team members have strong competences levels and language competence levels and are quite fluent in speaking native language Swedish and international language, English and have area of interest is cardiology. They perform different responsibilities in general department and emergency department of Cardiology in Ryhov, hospital, Jönköping according to the situation.

A person is Dr. Anders Bill, whose role is Junior Practitioner and his major responsibilities are to visit particular cardiology ward, prepare the patient medical history and call meeting before starting the ward-round meeting. He has full time work experience 2-3 years. He has educational competence MD, MDCM, Cand.med [70] in figure-39.

Similarly, a person is Dr. Inger Johansson, whose role is Senior Practitioner and his major responsibilities are to visit particular cardiology ward often and arrange some education learning opportunities for medical students during the ward-round process. He has educational competence MD, MDCM, Cand.med, DO[70] and full time work experience 5-6 years.

A person is Fridell Gunilla, whose role is Head Nurse and her major responsibility is to get patient-bed availability status from the information system: EBBA (Patient-admit status system) and maintain the ward. She has educational competence BSN, BNurs, BScN, BSc, MN [70] and full time work experience 5-6 years.

Similarly, a person is Susanne Ålgren, whose role is Additional Nurse and her major responsibilities are to receive medical test results from laboratory database and get patient record from the information system COSMIC (Patient Electronic Record System) and maintains the ward. She has full time work experience 2-3 years and has educational competence BSN, BNurs, BScN, BSc, MN [70].

A person is Marit Gustafsson, whose role is Occupational Therapist and her major responsibility are to review medication, mental state of patient, risks factors in certain situations and necessary arrangement in the ward round [31]. She has educational field psychology and full time work experience 5-6 years. She has educational competence MOST, MAOT, MOT, OTD, Dr.OT [70].

Similarly, A person is Dr. Yvonne Turesson, whose role is Consultant and his major responsibilities are to visit particular cardiology ward, contribute in decision making process and manage ward-round resource patient treatment related and educational learning opportunities resources like conferences, seminars, guest lecturers for medical students For example,. He has educational field is cardiology and specialization in surgery. He belongs to specialized medical practitioner group and having educational competence MBBS, MBChB, BMed, Dr.med, Ph.d. he has full time work experience 8-10 years in particular field.

Results

This screenshot shows the Protégé interface for the class **DesignatedTeam2**. The left sidebar displays a class hierarchy with **DesignatedTeam** selected. The main window shows the class description: "DesignatedTeam2 Consist of Multidisciplinary Professional for patient treatment concern's". The "Types" section lists **DesignatedTeam** and **Thing**. The "Property assertions" section lists several roles: **hasOccupationalTherapistRole OccupationalTherapist**, **hasConsultantRole Consultant**, **hasJuniorPractitionerRole JuniorPractitioner**, **hasSeniorPractitionerRole SeniorPractitioner**, **hasHeadNurseRole HeadNurse**, **hasAdditionalNurseRole AdditionalNurse**, **hasRole OccupationalTherapist**, and **hasRole Consultant**.

This screenshot shows the Protégé interface for the class **JuniorPractitioner**. The left sidebar displays a class hierarchy with **JuniorPractitioner** selected. The main window shows the class description: "Junior Practitioner". The "Types" section lists **GeneralPractitionerRole**, **JuniorPractitionerRole**, **MedicalPractitionerRole**, **Role**, and **Thing**. The "Property assertions" section lists several properties: **speakLanguage Swedish**, **initiatePreWardroundProcess PreWardroundProcess1**, **hasEducationalField Cardiology**, **hasWorkExperience 2-3_Years**, **hasInterculturalSensitivity Accpetance-HighLevel**, **manageGeneralWard CardiologyGeneralWard**, **participatePreWardroundActivity Activity3:ToPrepareCriticalMedicalHisotryOfCertainDisease**, and **hasGeneralCompetence PlanningAndDesigningAbility-ExcellentLevel**.

This screenshot shows the Protégé interface for the class **AdditionalNurse**. The left sidebar displays a class hierarchy with **AdditionalNurse** selected. The main window shows the class description: "AdditionalNurse is the Role which is working in Ryhov, Hospital, Jönköping". The "Types" section lists **AdditionalNurseRole**, **MedicalNurseRole**, **Role**, and **Thing**. The "Property assertions" section lists several properties: **hasEducationalField Nursing**, **relateToProfessionalGroup NursingProfessionalGroup1**, **isAssignRole Susanna_Ålgren**, **hasInterculturalSensitivity Accpetance-HighLevel**, **workAt RyhovHospital**, **hasWorkExperience 2-3_Years**, **performWardroundTask Task3:PatientTreatmentPlanningProcess**, **acheiveGoal Goal1:ToAcheiveEffectiveDecisionMaking**, and **experienceLevel EducationalLevel-Strong**.

This screenshot shows the Protégé interface for the class **Consultant**. The left sidebar displays a class hierarchy with **Consultant** selected. The main window shows the class description: "Consultant it the senior Medical Practitioner who take decision in patient treatment". The "Types" section lists **ConsultantRole**, **MedicalPractitionerRole**, **Role**, and **Thing**. The "Property assertions" section lists several properties: **isAssignRole Yvonne_Turesson**, **proposeTreatmentPlan LongTermTreatmentPlan1**, **hasWorkExperience 8-10_Years**, **visitWardOftenly CardiologyGeneralWard**, **acheiveGoal Goal1:ToAcheiveEffectiveDecisionMaking**, **relateToProfessionalGroup MedicalSpecialistGroup1**, **hasEducationalField HeartSurgery**, **delieverTeachingLecture Abid_Ali**, and **generalCompetenceLevel GeneralCompetenceLevel-Strong**.

This screenshot shows the Protégé interface for the class **WardroundProcess**. The left sidebar displays an "Inferred class hierarchy" for **WardroundProcess**, showing it as a subclass of **Process**, with **PostWardroundProcess** and **PreWardroundProcess** as subclasses of **WardroundProcess**. The main window shows the class description: "WardroundProcess". The "Equivalent classes" section is empty. The "Superclasses" section lists **Process**. The "Inferred anonymous superclasses" section is empty. The "Members" section lists **WardroundProcess1**. The "Disjoint classes" section lists **PostWardroundProcess**.

5.14.5. Evaluation

At this stage, the evaluation is the vital activity to show the quality and assurance that all the requirements are met in ontology development process. So it is key thing to check the inconsistency in the domain's knowledge in the ontology development process. Evaluation is handled through following ways:

1. Through Protégé 4.0.2 DL Query Editor

In Protégé 4.0, SPARQL query is not entertained but we can use DL Query Tab to justify competence question in our report. DL query can be presented in two ways [76]: Class Query and Individual Query.

Serial No.	Competence Questions	DL-Query Structure	Results
1	Who are the members involved in ward-round?	Role and initiateProcess value WardroundProcess1	Medical Individuals <ul style="list-style-type: none"> OccupationalTherapist AdditionalNurse SeniorPractitioner HeadNurse Consultant JuniorPractitioner
2	Which medical staff visit the medical ward regularly?	Role and visitWardDaily value CardiologyGeneralWard	Role <ul style="list-style-type: none"> AdditionalNurse JuniorPractitioner HeadNurse
3	Which medical staff visit the medical ward often?	Role and visitWardOftenly value CardiologyGeneralWard	Role <ul style="list-style-type: none"> OccupationalTherapist Consultant SeniorPractitioner
4	Which is the role of Senior physician?	Person and hasRole SeniorPractitioner	Instance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inger_Johansson

Table-5 Evaluation Results

In the figure-51, we describe to show the result with different set queries in the DL-query Tab editor the

2. Manual Assessment

The evaluation activity is also verified and evaluated through domain expert's assessment especially in our research study healthcare. The domain's experts are responsible to give feedback for improvements.

5.14.6. Final Remarks

This chapter concludes the results in the form of ontology models which are used in ontology development. This chapter also links the connection between research methods and ontology development results for understanding. For example, I have presented proposed ontology models in the modelling workshop as results which describe the working pattern of domain's scenario. I have also used some key concepts for reusing in my development from the literature review [32] in my ontology development.

This chapter describes the implementation of the ontology based models that presents main scenario. For the evaluation is concerned, this chapter helps to evaluate the results through different ways. Especially, DL Query structure is used in the Protégé 4.0.2 and also used manual assessment by the domain experts in modelling workshop session. The evaluation of the results is testified through competence questions (Appendix section 8.7) which the end-user expects from the ontology based model implementation.

6. Conclusion and Future Work

6.1. Conclusion

This research dissertation covers information logistics and ontology development in the healthcare area. The main focus is to address information flow problems in ward-round hospital infrastructure and need to know, what the needs of the individual's roles and what the demands of the ward-round in given context. The existing situation of the ward-round is not very efficient to achieve quality patient's treatment process. So, the main contribution is to develop an ontology based model that can be used to support improvement of information flow in the ward-round patient treatment process in healthcare sector. To fix information problems, I have proposed ontology based model that supports to fix information flow problems and increase the efficiency of healthcare services according to the situation in the ward-round. This ontology based model can be considered as foundation to develop a software product with the help of IT practitioners and developers to fulfill the medical practitioner's demands in ward-round.

I have conducted two useful modeling workshops with domain experts to get the specific information to solve the current problems in ward-round of healthcare unit. This thesis work mentions what are the contribution of the roles in the situation, what are the competences that are required to perform certain tasks, what are the goals and what are the processes required to initiate different activities in the ward-round processes for quality patient's treatment procedure. In this dissertation, I have presented an ontology based model for the ward-round process in the healthcare area that is truly contribution to support a solution to fix information flow problems in the ward-round on a hospital unit.

This ontology based model describes information flow in the ward-round processes in such a way that domain's users can easily get relevant information according to their demand and needs. This ontology based model focuses on three major processes of ward-round: Pre ward-round process, Ward-round process and Post ward-round process in the patient treatment procedure. Multidisciplinary professionals make different teams to perform certain tasks to achieve goals and initiate different processes at different stages of Ward-round. This ontology based model also describes healthcare professional's competences to ensure the quality of involved participant roles which are responsible for conducting the ward-round.

This ontology based model also focuses on the needs of individuals with their competences according to their roles while executing tasks in the ward-round processes. This ontology based model can be helpful for medical practitioners to take some vibrant decisions while patient treatment in ward-round. I have built an ontology for healthcare sector with the help of workshops with domain experts who had given sensitive information regarding the ward-round issues and individuals they are involved in different activities. The important thing is to select the right methodology steps for the ontology development. I have chosen hybrid methodology explained in section 3.5.1 and also used existing ontology concepts like competences from literature [32] in the ontology that is being used for development.

I have tried to highlight the importance of the ontology development in healthcare. It is concluded that my model (Ontology-based model for the Ward-round Process) can be the real contribution to fix information flow problems and to provide a modeling solution for medical practitioner's needs and demand and helps for taking vibrant decisions in Ward-round

healthcare area with the help of ontology development. I have focused to target particular ward-round in specific department of any organization, so most of the discussion which I did in this thesis is related to Cardiology and its related departments. I have tried to present the structure of the ontology development in generic way that any ontology developer can develop and utilize the same ontology pattern for other area of healthcare for reusability is concerned.

I have discussed different existing ontologies of healthcare and bio-informatics like EcoCyc (gives comprehensive encyclopedia of biology), TABIS (is complete an application for biologist for acquiring information from the system), GALEN (which is specified for gene product) in our thesis. These existing ontologies target different perspective of healthcare like microbiology, molecular biology information system and gene product is concerned, but my ontology based model is only targeting and describing the importance of Ward-round and also addressing key issues in ward-round processes for quality patient treatment in healthcare sector through ontology development.

From the research point of view, we have chosen mixed method design process which is the combination of Action research and Constructive research; it is quite suitable for our thesis's work because it fulfills the requirements of action research with set objectives which are quite closer to healthcare. For ontology development point of view, different methodologies have been discussed in this thesis, but we have customized Methontology and Dove (Toronto Virtual Enterprise) ontology and constructed Hybrid methodology for our research thesis's discussion.

This thesis work also keeps the openness for multidisciplinary professional to access the optimal information according to their demands from different information's channels at right time at right location. This characteristic allows hospital personal to receive timely relevant information according to different scenarios in the patient treatment procedure.

6.2. Future Work

This thesis work is laid down foundation for further work in the area of ward-round process in the healthcare sector. Through literature review and intensive study of ward-round, we can conclude that there are certain research areas in ward-round study related to patient treatment in healthcare organization. These research areas are focused on "*Inter-professional interactions during the ward-round process and doctor-patient communication, Un-met patient needs after round, Optimising teaching: patient and student perspective, Relatives: role and place, Consultant vs. the junior doctor round, Quality of notes and patient communication, Alternatives to the bed-to-bed round*" [6]. We can also design a model by using knowledge base that can be more intelligent to get more relevant and necessary information according to demands of the domain users [3]. These research areas are out of the scope of this these but we can take them as research area for further studies in healthcare sector.

7. References

- [1] Dr. Wolfgang Deiters Fraunhofer. (2003) “Information Logistics, E- Healthcare and Trust”, Kerstin Heuwinkel ISST Emil-Figge-Strabe 91 4427 Dortmund-ermany, IADIS International Conference e-Society.
- [2] Banafsheh Khademhosseini, Muhammad Tahir Khan. (2009) “Tools and Organizational Measures to Improve Information Flow”, Master Thesis Informatics, , School of Engineering, Jonkoping, Sweden.
- [3] Muhammad Ayub, Muhammad Jawad. (2009) “Structuring and Modelling Competences in the Healthcare Area with the help of Ontologies”, Master Thesis Informatics, School of Engineering, Jonkoping, Sweden.
- [4] Dennis Gillings. (2003) “Building the national health information infrastructure for patient health care services, public health, and research”, BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making, USA.
- [5] Reuben Arasaratnam. (2009) “Medical Ward rounds”, StudentBMJ, Volume 17, DOI: 10.1136/sbmj.b576.
- [6] James A. O’Hare. (2008) “Anatomy of the ward round”, Eurpean Federation of Internal Medicine, Published by © Elsevier B.V.
- [7] Ann Bowling. (2002) “Research Methods in Health: Investigating health and health services”, 2nd Edition, Open University Press Buckingham, Philadelphia, PA 19106, USA.
- [8] IEEE, (1996) “Standard for Developing Software Life Cycle Processes”, ISBN: 1-55937-588-4, IEEE Computer Society, New York, USA.
- [9] R. Burke Johnson, Anthony J. Onwuegbuzie, (2004) “Mixed Methods Research: A Research Paradigm Whose Time Has Come”, Educational Researcher, Vol. 33, pp. 14-26.
- [10] Caterina Arcidiacono, Richard Velleman, Fortuna Procentese, (2009) “A Synergy Between Action-Research and a Mixed Methods Design for Improving Services and Treatment for Family Members of Heavy Alcohol and Drug Users”, Journal of Community & Applied Psychology, Published by © John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, Soc. Psychol., 20: 95-109.
- [11] R. Burke Johson, Anthony J. Onwuegbuzie, Lisa A. Turner, (2007) “Toward a Definition of Mixed Methods Research”, Journal of Mixed Methods Research Vol. 1 No. 2, pp. 112-133, Published by © Sage Publications.
- [12] Dr. Ann Curry, (2005) “Action Research in Action: Involving Students and Professionals”, World Library and Information Congress: 71th IFLA General Conference and Council “Libraries – A voyage of discovery”, Oslo, Norway.
- [13] Julienne Meyer, (2000), “Using Qualitative Methods in Health Related Action Research”, Education and debate, BMJ, Vol. 320 pp. 178-81.
- [14] Mike Walsh, Gordon Grant, Zoe Coleman, (2007) “Action Research- A Necessary Complement to Traditional Health care Science”, Health Care Anal, Vol. 16, pp: 127-144 © Springer Science + Business Media, LLC.
- [15] Alberas Caplinskas, Olegas Vasilecas, (2004) “Information Systems Research Methodologies and Models”, International Conference on Computer Systems and Technologies- CompSysTech’s 2004.
- [16] Anna-Liisa Lindholm, (2008), “A Constructive Study on Creating Core Business relevant CREM Strategy and Performance Measures”, Printed by © Emerald Group Publishing, Facilities, Vol. 26, No. 7-8, pp. 343-358.

References

-
- [17] Natalya F. Noy and Deborah L. McGuinness, (2000), "Ontology Development 101: A Guide to Creating Your First Ontology", Stanford University, Stanford, CA, 94305.
- [18] Oscar Corcho, Mariano Fernandez-Lopez, Asuncion Gomez-Perez, Angel Lopez-Cima, (2005), "Building Legal Ontologies with METHONTOLOGY and WebODE" V.R. Benjamins et al. (EDs.): Law and the Semantic Web, LNAI 3369, pp. 142-157 © Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg 2005.
- [19] Dean Jones, Trevor Bench-Capon, Pepijn Visser, (1998), "Methodologies For Ontology Development", Department of Computer Science, University of Liverpool, Liverpool, U.K, L69 7ZF.
- [20] Mariano Fernandez Lopez, Asuncion Gomez-Perez, Juan Pazos Sierra, (1999), "Building a Chemical Ontology Using Methontology and the Ontology Design Environment", © 1999 IEEE.
- [21] Asuncion Gomez-Perez, Mariano Fernandez, Antonio J. de Vicente, (1995), "Towards a Method to Conceptualize Domain Ontologies", Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, 28660, Madrid, Spain.
- [22] Mariano Fernandez, Asuncion Gomez-Perez, Natalia Juristo, (1997), "METHONTOLOGY: From Ontological Art Towards Ontological Engineering", AAI Technical Report SS-97-06. Compilation copyright © 1997, AAI (www.aaai.org).
- [23] Annika Öhgren, Kurt Sandkuhl, (2005), "Towards a Methodology for Ontology development in Small and Medium-sized Enterprises", IADIS International Conferences on Applied Computing.
- [24] Fernandez Lopez, M., (1999), "Overview of Methodologies for Building Ontologies", Proceeding of the IJCAI-99 workshop on Ontologies and Problem solving Methods, ISSN 1613-0073, Vol. 18. CEUR Workshop Proceedings, Stockholm, Sweden.
- [25] Graciela Brusa, Ma. Laura Caliusco, Omar Chiotti, (2006), "A Process for Building a Domain Ontology: an Experience in Developing a Government Budgetary Ontology ", Conferences in Research and Practice in Information Technology, Vol. 72., Australasian Ontology Workshop (AOW), Hobart, Australia.
- [26] Michael Gruninger, Mark S. Fox, (1995), "Methodology for the Design and Evaluation of Ontologies", Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Toronto, Canada M5S 1A4.
- [27] Paula Stanley, (1998), " Structuring Ward Rounds for Learning: Can Opportunities be Created ", MEDICAL EDUCATION, Vol. 32, ppt. 239-243, © Blackwell Science Ltd.
- [28] Jake Harvey, Max Pickard, Mohammad Nunhuck, (2008), "End of the Paper Trail: Moving towards a Paperless Ward round", Psychiatric Bulletin (2008), Vol. 32, ppt. 67-68, DOI: 10.1192/pb.bp.106.014225.
- [30] Magdalen Fiddler, Gunilla Borglin, Adrian Galloway, Carl Jackson, Linda McGowan, Karian Lovell, (2010), "Once-a-Week Psychiatric Ward Round or Daily Inpatient Team meeting? A Multidisciplinary Mental Health Team's Experience of New ways of Working", International Journal of Mental Health Nursing, Vol. 19. ppt. 119-127, DOI:10.1111/J.1447-0349.2009.00652.X.
- [31] Acute Care Forum, Sean Lennon, (2009), "Service Governance and Operations Directorates: Policy for Ward Rounds & Care Planning for In-Patients", Manchester Mental Health and Social Care Trust, Manchester, UK.
- [32] Vladimir Tarasov, Kurt Sandkuhl, Magnus Lundqvist, (2009), "An Ontology-Based Competence Model for Collaborative Design", Virtual Team Leadership & Collaborative Engineering Advancements: Contemporary Issues and Implications. Ned Kock (Ed.). Information Science Reference, 2009, pp. 188-202.
- [33] Maria Tavares Cavalcanti, Catarina Magalhaes Dahl, Maria Cecilia Araujo de Carvalho, Elie Valencia, (2009), "Criteria for Admission and Continuity of Health care in

References

- Psychosocial Healthcare Services, City of Rio de Janeiro, Southeastern Brazil”, CAPS admission and Continuity of Care, *Rev Saude Publica* 2009, Vol. 43 Supl. 1.
- [34] Dominique-Jeanne Lepaux, (2001), ”Improving the quality of the Admission Process in a French Psychiatric Hospital: Impact on the Expertise of the Professional Team”, *International Journal of Quality in Health Care* 2001; Vol. 13, Number 4, ppt. 333-338, © Oxford University Press.
- [35] Thomas Secrest, (2009), “Guide to Taking a Patient History”, *Patient Interview Guide*.
- [36] Patricia A. Barrier, James T. C. Li, Norman M. Jensen, (2003), “Two Words to Improve Physician-Patient Communication: What Else?”, © Mayo Foundation for Medical Education and Research, 2003, Vol. 78, ppt. 211-214.
- [37] Jonathan Price, Laurence Leaver, (2002), “ABC of Psychological Medicine Beginning Treatment”, © BMJ, Vol. 325.
- [38] Uday S. Karmarkar and Vandana Mangal, (2004), ”Information Technology Impact on Business Practices: “Managing in the Information Economy Chapter No: 16” The UCLA BIT Project”, UCLA Anderson Graduate School of Management, 110 Westwood Plaza, Los Angeles, ISSN 1934-3221, V CA 90095-1481, Vol. 1, ppt. 385-411, © Springer US.
- [40] Stephen B. Harsh, (2005), “Management Information Systems”, Department of Agricultural Economics, Michigan State University, USA.
- [41] Kurt Sandkuhl, (2008), “Information Logistics in Networked Organizations: Selected Concepts and Applications”, *ICEIS 2007, LNBIP 12*, pp.43-54, © Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg.
- [42] Anders Carstensen, Kurt Sandkuhl, (2005), “Coordination of Inter-Organizational Healthcare Processes: Experiences from Combining Process and Document Centred Modelling”, *International Workshop on Communication and Coordination in Business Processes*, Kiruna, Sweden.
- [43] Kerstin Heuwinkel, Dr. Wolfgang Deiters, (2004), “Information Logistics, E-Healthcare and Trust”, 44227 Dortmund, Germany.
- [44] Anouk Willems, Ing. Jan Willems, Prof. Dr. Ir. Andrzej Hajdasinski, (2009), “Information Logistics Research Report: Framework in the Healthcare Industry”, NRI Working Paper no. 09-04, ISSN 1872-3934, © NRI Working Paper Series, The Netherlands.
- [45] Magnus Lundqvist, Kurt Sandkuhl, Tatiana Levashova, Alexander Smirnov, (2005), ”Context-Driven Information Demand Analysis in Information Logistics”, © 2005 American Association for Artificial Intelligence (www.aaai.org).
- [46] Kirsten Norgaard, Charlotte Ringsted, Diana Dolmans, (2004), “Validation of a Checklist to Assess Ward Round Performance in Internal Medicine”, © Blackwell Publishing Ltd *MEDICAL EDUCATION* 2004, Vol. 38, ppt. 700-707.
- [47] P.J.McLeod,* MD, (1986), “A Successful Formula for Ward Rounds”, *CMAJ*, Vol. 134. Montreal.
- [48] Richard Hodgson, A. Jamal, B. Gayathri, (2005), “A Survey of Ward Round Practice”, *Psychiatric Bulletin*, Vol. 29, ppt. 171-173.
- [49] Laura Birtwistle, Fudith M Houghton, Helen Rostill, (2000), “A Review of a Surgical Ward Round in a Large Paediatric Hospital: Does It Achieve Its Aims”, © Blackwell Science Ltd, *MEDICAL EDUCATION* 2000, Vol. 34, ppt. 398-403.
- [50] Nicholas J.Fox, (1993), “Discourse, Organization and the Surgical Ward Round”, *Sociology of Health & Illness* Vol. 15 No. 11993 ISSN 0141-9889.
- [51] Martin Talbot, (2000), “An Interview Study of the Working Ward Round as an Instrument of Experiential Learning in Postgraduate Medical Education: A Preparatory Exploration”, *Journal of Vocational Education and Training*, Vol. 52. Central Sheffield University Hospitals NHS Trust, United Kingdom.

References

-
- [52] Thomas R. Gruber, (1993), "A Translation Approach to Portable Ontology Specifications", Appeared in Knowledge Acquisition, 5(2): 199-200.
- [53] Robert Neches, Richard Fikes, Tim Finin, Thomas Gruber, Ramesh Patil, Ted Senator, William R. Swartout, (1991), "Enabling Technology for Knowledge Sharing", © AAAI, 1991, AI MAGZINE.
- [54] Nicola Guarino, Pierdaniele Giaretta, (1995), "Ontologies and Knowledge Bases Towards a Terminological Clarification". Towards Very Large Knowledge Bases, IOS Press 1995, Amsterdam.
- [55] Bill Swartout, Ramesh Patil, Kevin Knight, Tom Russ, (1997), "Toward Distributed Use of Large Scale Ontologies", AAAI Technical Report SS-97-06, Compilation copyright © 1997, AAAI (www.aaai.org).
- [56] Rudi Studer, V.Richard Benjamins, Dieter Fensel, (1998), "Knowledge Engineering: Principles and Methods", Vol. 25, ppt. 161-197.
- [57] Mohamed Keshk, Sally Chambless, (2008), "Model Driven Ontology: A New Methodology for Ontology Development", Raytheon Company, Largo, Florida, USA.
- [58] York Sure, Steffen Staab, Rudi Struder, (2003), "On-To-Knowledge Methodology (OTKM)", Karlsruhe, Germany.
- [59] Dejan LAVBIC and Marjan KRISPER, (2007), "Rapid Ontology Development", Trazaska 25, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia.
- [60] Wullianallur Raghupathi, Amjad Umar, "An Archetype Pattern Driven Approach to Ontology development in healthcare Information Systems" , Graduate School of Business, Fordham University, 113 W, 60th Street, NY, 10023, USA.
- [61] Gajun Ganendran, Quynh-Nhu Tran, Pronab Ganguly, Pradeep Ray, Graham Low, (2002), "An Ontology-driven Multi-agent Approach for Healthcare", School of Information Systems, Technology and Management, Kensington, NSW 2052, Australia, ISBN 0958537097.
- [62] Christine Kunzmann, Andreas Schmidt, (2006), "Ontology-based Competence Management of Healthcare Training Planning: A Case Study", Proceedings of the International Conference on Knowledge Management (I-KNOW'06), Graz, 2006.
- [63] Jinagbo Dang, Amir Hedayati, Ken Hampel, Candemir Toklu, (2008), "An Ontological Knowledge Framework for Adaptive Medical Workflow", Journal of Biomedical Informatics, Vol. 41, ppt. 829-836.
- [64] H. Sofia Pinto, J.P. Martins, (2000), "Reusing Ontologies", In AAAO 2000, Spring Symposium on Bringing Knowledge to Business Processes.
- [65] Olivier Bodenreider, Robert Stevens, (2006), "Bio-Ontologies: Current trends and future Directions", Briefings in BioInformatics, Vol. 7 No. 3, ppt. 256-274, © Published by Oxford University Press.
- [66] Ingrid M. Keseler, Cesar Bonavides-Martinez, Julio Collado-Vides, (2009), "EcoCyc: A comprehensive view of Escherichia col Biology", Nucleic Acids Research, Vol. 37, Database Issue DOI:10.1093.
- [67] Robert Stevens, Patricia Baker, Sean Bechhofer, Gary Ng, Alex Jacoby, Norman W. Paton, Carole A. Goble, Andy Brass, (2000), "TAMBIS: Transparent Access to Multiple Bioinformatics Information Sources", BIOINFORMATICS Application Note, Vol.16 No. 2, ppt. 184-185.
- [68] Al Rector JE Rogers P Pole, (1996), "The Galen High Level Ontology" Accepted for Medical Informatics in Europe (MIE), Copenhagen.
- [69] Barry Smith, Jennifer Williams, Steffen Schulze-Kremer, (2003), "The Ontology of the Gene Ontology", Published in proceedings of AMIA Symposium.
- [70] http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/First_professional_degree.

References

- [71] Shirley Rigby, (2008), "Management Plans", StudentBMJ, Vol.16, www.student.bmj.com.
- [72] Jonathan Price, Laurence Leaver, (2002), "ABC of Psychological Medicine Beginning Treatment", Clinical Review, BMJ, Vol. 325, www.bmj.com.
- [73] William T. Branch, David Kern, Paul Haidet, Peter Weissmann, Catherine F. Gracey, Gary Mitchell, Thomas Inui, (2001), "Teaching the Human Dimensions of Care in Clinical Settings", JAMA, Vol. 286, No. 9, © American Medical Association.
- [74] Telematic Multidisciplinary Assistive Technology Education, Levels of Education. [Online]. Available: <http://www.fernuni-hagen.de/FTB/telemate/database/isced.htm> (Acc. 2009-05-08).
- [75] <http://ezinearticles.com/?Kinds-of-Diseases&id=244515> (by Michael Russell)
- [76] <http://protegewiki.stanford.edu/wiki/DLQueryTab>

8. Appendix

Requirement Specification

8.1. Task I: Motivating the Scenario

This step of methodology supports requirement elicitation process in ontology development process.

8.2. Requirement Engineering

For good understanding of the current case study (ward-round decision making process) in healthcare is achieved through the first modelling session by different experts of this real time project in healthcare industry.

8.3. Notes for Understanding for healthcare case study

Nowadays, effective, efficient patient's treatment is prominent and valuable in healthcare business. Different objects (Domain experts: Consultant, Senior & Junior Physicians, Head Nurse, Assistant Nurse, Occupational Therapist, Laboratory Personnel, etc. Resources: Information sources: EBBA, Cosmic, Laboratory database, environment: Hospital, equipments, etc) are involved for patient's requirements gathering and enhance pace of decision making in patient's treatment process. We have to focus to establish some intelligent procedures which support patient's treatment facilities accordingly, efficiently and effectively. "Ward-round" is an intelligent decision making procedure which used in the healthcare units.

The concept of "Ward-round" is the consortium of different domain individuals with different competences and profiles are involved and gathered to analyze the current status of patient's history and diagnose the right choice for the patient's medication point of view.

If you we take overview of old working style of "Ward-round" then we can analyze that domain participants with different competences and skills are gathered at certain designated time (9:00 A.M) and get the patient's routine status manually. The domain experts (Senior physicians, Junior physicians, Nurses, Assistant Nurses and occupational therapists) are got their respective information from manually system and analyze the patient-history and prescribe the diagnosis either patient should admit in the "ward" or somewhere else (home-based health care service). In manual work, The routine patient's medical history is judged through observations in day and night patient's reactions and laboratory report's status while monitoring at 7:30 A.M to the senior physicians or Junior physicians on daily basis before meeting start at 9:00 A.M. This "ward-round" is very time consuming and having no authentication of information provided by the concerning person due to human mistakes.

In the "ward-round" phenomenon, special visits are due by the senior medical staff (Consultant, senior physicians, surgeon, nurses, assistant surgeon and occupational therapists) in certain days (Monday, Wednesday, Friday) of week and rest of other days (Tuesday,

Thursday) other staff (Junior physicians, Nurses, Assistant Nurses, occupational therapists) are involved to analyze and look after the patient's treatment.

For enhancing the patient's treatment pace and the confirmation of vacant beds availability for routine-wise patients, emergency-based patient's, referred from other healthcare unit patient's admit in certain ward. For analyzing and assessment of the current situation of "ward-round", there should be integrated information systems which provide relevant information efficiently and effectively according to the patient's treatment demands and needs. In ward management, head nurse has responsibility to inform acute clinic examination team at certain time (11: 00 A: M) so that they can prioritize the patient's admit in the healthcare unit according to the patient's seriousness in treatment. Acute clinic examination is performed by the senior medical staff and define the procedure for patient's admit (Patient-admit process) in the ward or somewhere else with the help of ward management procedure for the availability of beds in the certain ward. The degree of patient-admit process is handled through bed availability status of the certain ward.

In every morning at certain time (9:00), medical staff with different competencies, profiles and having different roles receive particular information in the form of reports from different information channels like EBBA (Patient-admit status system), EMR (Electronic medical record system), database which is connected to pathology laboratory regarding a particular patient. These systems are mutually integrated and sharing the information in real-time manner to support intelligent decision making in patient's treatment in the healthcare unit.

Each "ward-round" is specialized accordingly in the healthcare unit so every assigned medical staff team is responsible for taking the decision in the patient's treatment in the healthcare unit. For enhancing the intra communication among different "word-rounds", every "ward-round" should be in open mode so that medical staff can communicate, discuss and hire to facilitate the patient's treatment handsomely.

Domain Ontology: Healthcare Business Sector

8.4. Scope of the Ontology

The ontology based modelling is specific about ward-round decision making process in particular healthcare unit in healthcare business sector. The main emphasize and primary focus is to develop ontology based model which facilitate different experts or domain individuals with different competencies and professional skills who are gathered to analyze and evaluate current patient treatment process. They have different roles and performing different tasks by utilizing different resources to improve patient's treatment process efficiently and effectively. The important aspect of this ontology development is to incorporate existing ontologies of domain's related like: competencies and diseases in the current ontology development for reusability [3].

8.5. Purpose

The purpose of this ontological study is to design ontology based model that helps to share relevant information for decision making process in patient's treatment procedure in

healthcare business. The usage of ontology based modelling is to support certain activities of each task in the ward-round of hospital which address ward-round information flow problems in healthcare unit.

8.6. Domain Users

1. Consultant
2. Senior Physician
3. Junior Physician
4. Nurse
 - a. Head Nurse
 - b. Assistant Nurse
5. Occupational Therapists
6. Medical Student

8.7. Task 2: Competence Questions Pool

1. Who are the members involved in ward-round?
2. How many types of doctors there?
3. How many type of disease are seen in ward-round?
4. What are the types of competencies?
5. Who the person has competency in the ward-round?
6. Which medical staff have different responsibilities?
7. How many member of staff in the team?
8. Who medical staff visit the medical ward regularly?
9. Who medical staff visit the medical ward often?
10. What are resources are used in ward-round (decision making process)?
11. Which are the roles of Doctors?
12. Which are the roles of Head Nurses?
13. Which are the roles of Consultant?
14. Which are the roles of Occupational Therapists?
15. Which are the roles of Assistant Nurse?
16. Which are the roles of Medical Students?
17. Which are the roles of laboratory personnel?
18. Which are the roles of Senior Physicians?
19. How many hospital's wards are there?
20. Which ward is dedicated for the ward-round?
21. How many proficiency levels are there?
22. How to trace the availability of the beds?
23. How many information systems are used in ward-round (decision making process)?

8.8. Task 3: Glossary of Terms

Name	Synonym	Description	Type
Concept			
Hospital	-----	Hospital is the place where multidisciplinary professional of medicine serve to patient and provide medical facilities.	concept
Organization	-----	Organization is the entity of group of people who are organized to carry out common goals in any domain.	Concept
Ward-round	-----	Ward- round is the consortium where hospital's professional and resource personnel take decision making concerning patient's treatment process [6].	Concept
Pre Ward-round	-----	Pre Ward-round process is performed some pre-requisite tasks for ward-round process.	Concept
Post Ward-round	-----	Post Ward-round process is performed the tasks for patient's treatment evolution after the Ward-round activities.	Concept
Medical Department	Medical Unit	Medical department is the different units in the hospital according to nature of diseases.	Concept
Medical Member	Medical Personnel	Medical member is the participant who performs some medical responsibilities.	Concept
Medical Consultant	Medical personal	Medical consultant is the person who is senior in his field and having competences and skills to take initiatives.	Concept
Senior Practitioner	Medical Personal	Senior practitioner is the person who is senior guy and performing some delicate responsibilities like surgery etc.	Concept
Junior Practitioner	Medical Personal	Junior practitioner is the person who is qualified and assists the seniors.	Concept

Appendix

Medical Student	Medical Learner	Medical students are the participant who learns medical education.	Concept
Medical Administrator	Medical Admin	Medical Admin is the person who performs administrative responsibilities.	Concept
Nurse	Medical Personal	Nurse is the active participant in patient's treatment process and different medical operations.	Concept
Occupational Therapist	Medical Personal	Occupational Therapists are the trained person who performs some activities in treatment process.	Concept
Laboratory Personal	Medical Personal	Laboratory personal is the responsible for conducting patient medical test and results.	Concept
Information System	System	Information system is the corporate system that is an organized with combination of different resources and transforms and disseminated information in an organization.	Concept
Designated Team	Group of Person	Designated team is consists of some medical staff members to perform certain roles.	Concept
Patient	Sick person	Patient is the involved participant in the treatment process.	Concept
Medical Reports	Report	Patient related results report.	Concept
Users	Readers	All medical members in the healthcare that is used ontology based model in the hospital [3].	Concept
Hospital Equipment	-----	Medical equipment which are used in ward-round.	Concept
Patient Medical History	Report	Patient history is the resource in ward-round which is taken by nurse.	Concept
Share Patient Medical History	Report	Patient shared medical history is also resource to invite the other's department medical officer to assessment current patient diseases or illness.	Concept
Ward	Hospital	Ward is the place where patient is	Concept

Appendix

	unit	admitted for treatment	
General Ward	Hospital unit	General ward is the place where general patients are admitted for minor treatment.	Concept
Specialized Ward	Hospital unit	Specialized ward is the place where specific nature of illness patient is admitted.	Concept
Emergency Ward	Hospital unit	Emergency ward is the place where patient who meet accident are admitted.	Concept
Diseases	Complaint	Particular complaints which are received while treatment or inherited diseases.	Concept
Competence	Ability to perform	Competence is the criteria to evaluate the requirements of an individual for performing some tasks [3].	Concept
Occupational Competence	Ability to perform	It includes the educational level and experience level [32].	Concept
Culture Competence	Ability to perform	It includes the language and intercultural sensitivity level [32].	Concept
General Competence	Ability to perform	It includes generic good characteristics in the personal like leadership, efficiency.	Concept
Competence Selection Criteria	-----	It is the selection criteria for finding right proficiency level of involved personnel in patient's treatment process in ward-round.	Concept
Patient Treatment Agenda	Plan	It includes Disease centred, patient's agenda for treatment planning.	Concept
Patient Treatment plan	Procedure	Patient treatment is the kind of procedure for medication.	Concept
Process	Procedure	The input values from the users what he wants to search or desire to take from system for different tasks [3].	Concept
Tasks	-----	Task is the desire of state for achieving certain goals	Concept
Activities	Sequence of work	Activities are the sequence of work to perform certain task.	Concept
Educational Learning	-----	It includes some learning opportunities	Concept

Appendix

Opportunities		for students like conferences, seminar, tutorial lectures etc.	
Medical Case Study	-----	It is about previous case studies or legacy information related to concerning topic.	Concept
Occupational Group	-----	Reuse the concept of ISCO (International Standard Classification of Occupations)	Concept
Relation			
Uses (Organization, Resources)	-----	The organization uses the different resources in the organization.	Relation
Propose (Role, Resources)	-----	The different roles propose different resources according to their nature of role or tasks.	Relation
Utilizes (Process, Resources)	-----	Different patient's treatment process utilizes different processes.	Relation
Must have (Process, Activities)	-----	Different processes must have the activities during the patient treatment.	Relation
Must have (Process, Goals)	-----	Different processes must have goals during the patient treatment.	Relation
Must have (Process, Tasks)	-----	Different processes must have the tasks during the patient treatment.	Relation
Has (Goal, tasks)	-----	Each goal in the process in the process has multiple tasks to achieve this goal.	Relation
Belongs (Medical Staff, Organization)	-----	Multidisciplinary hospital professional belongs to organization	Relation
Has (Medical staff, Role)	-----	Medical staff has multiple roles to perform different tasks in the organization.	Relation
Decide (Role, Process)	-----	Different roles initiative different process.	Relation
Involve (Medical Staff, Processes)	-----	In the hospital, medical staff is involved to start different process.	Relation
Has-competence (Medical staff, Competence)	-----	Medical staff has different competences to perform different tasks and responsibilities in the organization.	Relation

Suggests (Process, Information Selection Criteria)	-----	Different processes suggest information criteria for selection of right person in the right task or responsibilities.	Relation
Contains (Organization, Ward)	-----	Organization has different wards according to the nature of diseases	Relation.
Follows (Process, Organization Rule)	-----	Every process in the organization must obey the rule of organization.	Relation
Has role (Person, role)	-----	Every involved person in the organization has own role and description.	Relation

Table-6 Glossary Of Terms

8.9. Concept Taxonomies

1. General Competence I [3]

Figure-52 General Competence

2. Occupational Competence II [3]

Figure- 53 Occupational Competence II

3. Occupational Competence II [3]

Figure -54 Occupational Competence

4. Department

Figure-55 Department

5. Proficiency Level

Figure-56 Proficiency Level

6. Rule

Figure-57 Rule

7. Medical Ward

Figure-58 Ward

8.10. Detail Diagram for Individual's Roles

The following diagrams are showing the detail interaction of different medical member's role in ward-round scenario.

Figure-60 Detail Description of Junior Practitioner Role